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D4.5 REPORT ON FAIR DATA ASSESSMENT TOOLSET AND BADGING SCHEME

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Abstract

Providing practical solutions for implementing FAIR principles throughout the lifecycle of research data is one of the main goals of the FAIRsFAIR project. This report provides an update of the FAIR assessment metrics developed by the task 4.5 team and describes in detail two practical tools for assessing the FAIRness of research data during data acquisition, and for data already archived in a trusted data repository. The tools are named FAIR-Aware, and F-UJI. The report also presents a badging scheme for visualising and sharing the FAIR level of individual datasets.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CMMI	Capability Maturity Model Integration
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
CODATA	Committee on Data for Science and Technology
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSW	Catalogue Services for the Web
DANS	Dutch National Centre of Expertise and Repository for Research Data
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCC	Digital Curation Centre
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EAN	European Article Number
EBNF	Extended Backus-Naur Form
EDMI	EOSC Datasets Minimum Information
EML	Ecological Modelling Language
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFISCO	GO FAIR International Support and Coordination Office
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IASSIST	International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology
INIST	Institut de l'information scientifique et technique

IRD	L'Institut de recherche pour le développement
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISO/TR	International Organization for Standardization - Technical Report
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LOV	Linked Open Vocabularies
METS	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MODS	Metadata Object Description Schema
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (National Research Data Infrastructure)
NFDI4Chem	Chemistry Consortium within the NFDI
NWO	De Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (Dutch Research Council)
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OAI-ORE	Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PANGAEA	Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science
PAV	Provenance, Authoring and Versioning
PID	Persistent Identifier
PROV-O	PROV Ontology
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFa	Resource Description Framework in Attributes
REST	Representational State Transfer
RFC	Request for Comments

ROR	Research Organization Registry
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SPDX	Software Package Data Exchange
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
URFIST	Unité Régionale de Formation à l'Information Scientifique et Technique
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WDS	World Data System
XSD	XML Schema Definition

Executive Summary

One of FAIRSF AIR's main objectives is to provide practical solutions for the use of the FAIR data principles throughout the research data life cycle in order to foster a FAIR data culture in a broad range of scientific disciplines. This report represents deliverable D4.5 (Report on FAIR data assessment toolset and badging scheme) of FAIRSF AIR's Work Package 4 (FAIR Certification), task 4.5 (FAIR data assessments: pilots). We describe in detail some of the core products of the FAIRSF AIR project designed to support the practical implementation of the FAIR principles.

Section 1 introduces the overall approach and methodology of this task and gives an update on the status of the **FAIRSF AIR Data Object Assessment Metrics**. Further, we present the scientific rationale and standardisation background for practical tests we designed for each metric.

Section 2 gives a detailed description of the tools developed and their practical application during pilot assessments performed in selected trustworthy data archives:

- **FAIR-Aware** which allows self-assessment of FAIR during data acquisition and documentation and aims to raise the awareness of FAIR.
- **F-UJI** which allows the automated assessment of the FAIRness of research data sets which already is archived in a trustworthy data repository.

Section 3 introduces suggestions for a **badging scheme** and badge design suitable to visualize and share the level of FAIR for individual data sets as well as its practical implementation based on the FAIRSF AIR metrics.

Section 4 gives an overview on measures to increase the **sustainability** of both tools and associated installations. It further gives an estimate on the **impact** of these tools and presents past and ongoing **adoption** stories and use cases.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Approach

The overall goal of task 4.5 is to support the assessment of data usability (or fitness for use) of individual datasets. The task uses pilot activities to establish requirements to support the assessment of data and data assets as FAIR and is aimed at providing practical means to perform these pilots.

We are focussing on research data, data which is observed, collected or measured for scientific purposes. The current deployment model is most functional for (meta)data deposited in a trustworthy data archive and assigned an persistent identifier, but there is future scope for deployment within pre-deposit research workflows or pre-persistent identifier phases of repository workflows (e.g. during appraisal at deposit).

To achieve the goals of the task we developed and implemented two important components:

- 1) Assessment metrics
- 2) Practical tools and tests to perform FAIR assessments

Both components are addressing priority recommendations of the 'Turning FAIR into reality' (Collins et al. 2018) report published by the European Commission. specifically: Rec. 8 (Facilitate automated processing), Rec. 12: (Develop metrics for FAIR Digital Objects) as well as Rec. 25 (Implement FAIR metrics to monitor uptake).

Figure 1: Research data lifecycle; figure adapted from (Mosconi et al., 2019) and scenarios of FAIR assessment of datasets therein see also M4.9 Report on Fair Data Assessment Mechanisms to Develop Pragmatic Concepts for Fairness Evaluation at the Dataset Level¹. Red dashed lines indicate scenarios addressed by the F-UJI and FAIR Aware tools.

For the design and implementation of these components we followed a use case based approach to define the required process and outcome of FAIRness evaluations and assessments. Therefore, we identified and explored eight different scenarios for assessments (Fig. 1) which can be performed at different stages of the research data lifecycle (Mosconi et al. 2019) with the involvement of different stakeholders and actors such as researchers, data stewards, data service providers and standards bodies. Out of these eight scenarios two scenarios were selected as priority use cases to be piloted in Task 4.5. More detailed information about the definition and scope of the use cases, as well as the choice to explore the two use cases mentioned in section 2, can be found in our previous report D4.1 Draft Recommendations on Requirements for Fair Datasets in Certified Repositories (Devaraju and Herterich 2020).

One use case is about **raising awareness of researchers about how to make their data FAIR** before they deposit their data in an appropriate data repository. The tool we developed during this task to achieve this is FAIR-Aware² which allows self-assessment of FAIR during data acquisition and documentation.

The other use case is the **assessment of the FAIRness of research data** which already is archived in a trustworthy data repository to evaluate their readiness for

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4118405>

² <https://fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>

re-use. We developed F-UJI³ during task 4.5 to perform machine based assessments of FAIR on research data.

Presenting the outcome of an assessment or test via a simplified graphical representation can provide an attractive and easy to understand way of communicating results to the users of products, and of providing credit to product developers. Here an intuitive ‘badging scheme’ is essential: Evaluations with binary (e.g. pass/fail) outcomes can be presented through more simplistic ‘badges’. In cases such as automated FAIR assessments where underlying tests are granular the level to which this detail is represented in a ‘badge’ must be considered in their design. In all cases it is valuable to provide those viewing badges with access to the underlying detail of test methodologies and outcomes. Although FAIR badging schemes and designs have been proposed (e.g. Doorn and Dillo 2017), they have not yet been tested or applied to a larger multidisciplinary sample of datasets.

F-UJI and FAIR Aware aim to provide the means to expand and improve the technical ecosystem for FAIR data (Collins et al. 2018). Both tools as well as the defined metrics will be described in detail within the following sections of this document. Further, we will introduce a badging scheme based on the results of FAIR assessments of the F-UJI tool which allows users to visualise and recognise the level of FAIRness of individual data sets.

While two use cases are being addressed in FAIRsFAIR, a number of additional use cases were identified during the early stages of the desk research. These are presented in Appendix B.

1.2 Metrics

The FAIR principles represent “domain-independent, high-level principles that can be applied to a wide range of scholarly outputs” (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Therefore, we have considered the broadest possible and most interdisciplinary range of applications and proposed domain agnostic metrics to evaluate research data FAIRness instead of community specifics. The FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics are based on the indicators proposed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group 2020), the WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use checklist (Austin et al. 2019) as well as on results of the FAIRdat⁴ and

³ <https://fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

⁴ <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/fairdat>

FAIREnough⁵ projects. We have improved the metrics at several stages, considering the feedback from FAIR stakeholders through, e.g., a focus group study, open consultation and pilot repositories.

Figure 2. An example of the hierarchical relationship between principle, metric and practical tests.

The metrics defined are core metrics focussing on generally applicable data and metadata characteristics.

As FAIR principles are quite abstract and rather generically defined from a higher perspective we specified one or more metrics for each FAIR principle. Since each metric can be tested in various means depending on data contexts and current best practises we additionally proposed one or more practical tests to evaluate datasets against a particular metric. This results in a hierarchical model for our metrics in which each FAIR principle is assigned several metrics, which in turn can be assigned several tests. For example, metric 'FsF-F1-02D' (Data is assigned a persistent identifier) can be evaluated by two practical tests (Fig. 2). The first test verifies if a given identifier is based on a known persistent identifier scheme or syntax and the second test checks if the identifier resolves to a digital resource (i.e., landing page) of the object. Such a hierarchical model is beneficial since it allows to aggregate scores resulting from the tests to communicate the FAIRness of a dataset as a whole, by principle or by metric individually.

Each metric is uniquely identified according to the following syntax (in EBNF notation):

```
FsFMetricLabel ::= "FSF-" ([FAIR] [0-9] ( "." [0-9] )? ) ( "-" [0-9] + ) ( 'M' | 'D' | 'MD' )
```

⁵

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf7t1Z9IOBoj5GgWqik8KnhtH3B819Ch6ID5KuAz7yn0I0Opw/viewform>

For example, the identifier of the metric ‘FsF-F1-02D’ starts with a project abbreviation for FAIRsFAIR (FsF), followed by the related FAIR principle identifier (F2) and a local identifier (01). The last part of the identifier refers to the resource that will be evaluated based on the metric, e.g., data (D), metadata (M) or both (MD).

Seventeen metrics have been defined and improved during an iterative process which involved several stakeholders such as a number of data publishers, international initiatives such as OGC, RDA and WDS as well as the EOSC FAIR working group. The latest version of the FAIRsFAIR metrics has been announced at the project’s website (<https://www.fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>) available for public comments. In addition, each publication-ready version of the metrics have been uploaded and published at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>) providing a long-term record of all versions and allowing others to cite them when re-using the metrics in other contexts. The table (Tab. 1) below shows the latest version of the metrics as well as prose descriptions of associated tests.

Ongoing iterative development of F-UJI has allowed us to specify these tests in more detail, a new version of the metrics which is included as appendix in this report and will be published at Zenodo following public consultation. This version also includes specifications and justifications for the scoring schemes used for each test to qualitatively and quantitatively assess each investigated data object.

Principle	Metrics	Practical Tests
F1	FsF-F1-01D Data is assigned a globally unique identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The object is identified by an unique identifier (GUID or IRI) that follows a proper syntax. • The identifier is web-accessible (not broken).
F1	FsF-F1-02D Data is assigned a persistent identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A data identifier is specified based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme suitable for research data. • The identifier is web-accessible, i.e., it resolves to a landing page with metadata of the data object.
F2	FsF-F2-01M Metadata includes descriptive core elements to support data findability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some metadata (at all) has been made available via common (web) standards. • Minimum core citation metadata is specified (creator, title, publication date, publisher, and identifier) • Minimum core descriptive metadata is specified (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) through appropriate metadata fields.

F3	FsF-F3-01M Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content • A data identifier is included in the metadata and it matches the identifier provided as part of the assessment request.
F4	FsF-F4-01M Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata of the object is retrievable programmatically through at least one of the following methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Structured data embedded in the landing page of the data object. ◦ Typed Links of metadata document or Signposting header links. ◦ Content negotiation with a PID provider service (e.g., DataCite).
A1	FsF-A1-01M Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata includes the level of data access (e.g., public, embargoed, restricted) and its access conditions using appropriate metadata fields. • Access level metadata is machine-readable, and this is verified against controlled vocabularies: http://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/access_rights/ http://purl.org/eprint/accessRights http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right
A1	FsF-A1-02M Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metadata URI's scheme is based on a common application protocol. • The metadata is accessible through the identifier provided.
A1	FsF-A1-03D Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data URI's scheme is based on a shared application protocol. • The data is accessible through the identifier provided.
A2	FsF-A2-01M Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.	Programmatic assessment of the preservation of metadata of a data object can only be tested if the object is deleted or replaced. So this test is only applicable for deleted, replaced or obsolete objects. Importantly, continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice. Therefore, we regard that the assessment of metric applies to at the level of a repository, not at the level of individual objects. For this reason, we excluded its assessment details from the F-UJI implementation.
I1	FsF-I1-01M Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	<p>The metadata of the object is available in a formal knowledge representation language, e.g., through at least one of the following mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parsable, structured data is embedded in the landing

		<p>page</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parsable, formal metadata (e.g., RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint.
I1	FsF-I1-02M Metadata uses semantic resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Namespaces of known semantic resources are present in the metadata of an object; exclude common namespaces (e.g., rdf, rdfs, xsd, owl) from the test.
I3	FsF-I3-01M Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata captures the relation between a data object and its related entity. The relation is expressed using a relation type according to PROV-O or DataCite relation types. Relations are preferably be expressed as actionable unique or persistent identifiers e.
R1	FsF-R1-01MD Metadata specifies the content of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata includes the type of the object and the technical properties of its data file such as format, size, observed or measured variables. Metadata values of the properties comply with the actual data file.
R1.1	FsF-R1.1-01M Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata contains license information represented using an appropriate metadata element. A standard, machine readable license is specified.
R1.2	FsF-R1.2-01M Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata includes properties representing data creation such as creator, contributors, creation and modification dates and version, source, and relations that indicate data creation activities. Provenance metadata is available in a machine-readable version of PROV-O or PAV.
R1.3	FsF-R1.3-01M Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata is available through at least one of the domain metadata standards listed in RDA Metadata Standards Catalog⁶.
R1.3	FsF-R1.3-02D Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data is available in a long-term file format as defined in ISO/TR 22299 Data is available in an open format (see e.g., https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_open_formats) Data is available in a scientific file format (see e.g., Library of Congress dataset formats, Wolfram Alpha supported file formats)

Table 1. FAIRsFAIR object assessment metrics and summary of practical tests.

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-standards-catalog-working-group.html>

1.3 Practical tests design and rationale

Based on these metrics, our implementation of specific machine based FAIR assessment test is following standards, community best practises and scientific rationale which have been used to implement the assessment tool F-UJI:

Findability:

Unique and persistent object identification: Here we distinguish between uniqueness (**FsF-F1-01D**) and persistence (**FsF-F1-02D**) of a given identifier. The EOSC PID policy requires a PID to be globally unique, persistent, and resolvable which requires managed and governed infrastructures (Valle et al. 2020). Since no registry of accordingly valid persistent identifiers exists, we use the DataCite identifier type vocabulary (DataCite Metadata Working Group 2019) except identifiers exclusively used for print products and physical entities (e.g., ISBN, EAN, ROR). In addition, identifiers listed in identifiers.org are regarded to be persistent since these are managed and maintained.

Descriptive core metadata: Determining 'rich' metadata required to support data discovery (**FsF-F2-01M**), depends on the discipline and user requirements. However, 'Findable', refers to descriptive metadata as defined in the OAIS reference model (International Organization for Standardization 2012) ;ISO 14721:2012; (C. A. Lee 2009). Our practical tests are based on recommendations for data citation such as those proposed by Force11 (Data Citation Synthesis Group 2014) as well as the guidelines proposed by Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) disciplinary best practices (ESIP Data Preservation and Stewardship Committee 2019). The International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology (IASSIST) (Mooney and Newton 2012) as well as the cross-domain data citation recommendations provided by DataCite (Fenner et al. 2019). In addition to citation metadata, abstract or summary and keywords are vital to describe essential aspects of a data object. Additionally, we followed Fenner et al. (2019)'s advice to include the resource type within the metadata to distinguish research data objects from other digital objects.

The resulting set of core metadata properties (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) aligns well with existing recommendations for data discovery and core metadata definition such as EOSC Datasets Minimum Information (EDMI; (Asmi et al. 2017), the DataCite Metadata Schema (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019), the W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices (Lóscio,

Burle, and Calegari 2017), and the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT-2) specification (Albertoni et al. 2020). Further these metadata properties are supported by most domain agnostic metadata standards such as Dublin Core⁷, DCAT-2, schema.org/Dataset⁸, and DataCite schema.

Our practical tests verify the presence of metadata and in particular the presence of core data citation or core descriptive metadata defined above.

Searchable metadata: Searchability and discoverability of data objects (**FsF-F4-01M**) requires implementing common web standards supported by major search engines as well as research data portals. We focus on three mainstream metadata provision methods:

- providing 'structured data' metadata embedded in the landing page of a data set
- enabling content negotiation to deliver e.g. community specific metadata
- providing typed or Signposting links leading to additional metadata representations

Regarding structured data, the use of Schema.org JSON-LD encoded metadata and embedding Dublin Core meta elements in the landing page (Kunze 1999) are very often used. Both became very common to support search engine indexing during the last years (Huber et al. 2021). Other popular methods to embed metadata on the landing page are RDFa Core (Adida et al. 2015), the microdata syntax (Nevile and Brickley 2018), or the OpenGraph protocol⁹.

The use of content negotiation to retrieve metadata is a W3C recommended approach to enable simple access to metadata for humans and machines and widely adopted by the research data community (see data on the Web recommendations by Loscio et al., 2016). This practice is currently gaining traction within the "open data" community through the emerging "content negotiation by profile" approach (Svensson, Atkinson, and Car 2019).

A currently emerging practice is providing links leading to external metadata descriptions within a landing page's HTML head section following the typed links convention (RFC8228,(Nottingham 2010)) or following the Signposting recommendation¹⁰ to include links in the HTTP response header (Van de Sompel and Nelson 2015).

⁷ <https://dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/>

⁸ <https://schema.org/Dataset>

⁹ <https://ogp.me/>

¹⁰ <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

All three practices above (structured data, content negotiation, and typed links) are verified in our implementation to test if an object's metadata is retrievable over the Web and to retrieve and parse the metadata required for the subsequent FAIR tests described in this document.

Verifying whether research data objects are ultimately included in common data catalogues is a challenge. Currently, we use the Google Dataset Search dataset as well as the interfaces provided by DataCite and Mendeley Data representing some of the leading interdisciplinary research data catalogues and search engines.

Inclusion of data identifiers: access to data objects (e.g. data files) is essential for and tested in **FsF-F3-01M**. The presence of data identifiers can be verified using domain agnostic standards (e.g. DataCite, schema.org/Dataset, and DCAT.) which provide specific metadata properties allowing us to specify data content in terms of e.g. download links. Further recognition of identifiers encoded in domain specific metadata standards such as EML, DDI or ISO19139 can be implemented. In addition, presence of data identifiers which have been made available through other mechanisms such as the above-mentioned typed links or Signposting type links can be verified.

Accessibility:

Access level specification: humans as well as machines need to understand given access rights and restrictions or rights in order to either retrieve the data accordingly or avoid unnecessary access attempts. The indication of access levels is also important due to the 'as open as possible' FAIR community consensus (e.g.(Mons et al. 2017) or (Boeckhout, Zielhuis, and Bredenoord 2018)). Therefore a practical test of the metric **FsF-A1-01M** can verify the presence of data access levels (e.g., public, embargoed, restricted) within appropriate metadata fields. It can also be verified that/if access levels are expressed using formal vocabularies and associated identifiers of e.g. the COAR controlled vocabulary for access rights¹¹, the Eprints AccessRights vocabulary encoding scheme¹², the EU publications access rights terms¹³, or the OpenAire access rights¹⁴ definition.

Data and metadata access protocols: metadata and data need to be accessible through a standard communication protocol (**FsF-A1-02M** and **FsF-A1-03D**). A variety of protocol standards have been defined during the last decades. However, some of

¹¹ http://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/access_rights/

¹² http://www.ukoln.ac.uk/repositories/digirep/index/Eprints_AccessRights_Vocabulary_Encoding_Scheme

¹³ <http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right>

¹⁴ https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/field_rights.html

them are deprecated (e.g., Apple Filing Protocol, Gopher, see e.g. (C. Lee 1999)), leaving only a comparatively small number of machines and human-friendly web protocols in use which include (s)http(s), (s)ftp, ssn, svn, telnet, rtsp and ws(s). A possible practical test we implemented is therefore to extract the URI scheme (RFC7595; (Thaler, Hansen, and Hardie 2015)) of a given URI and verify if the scheme corresponds to those shared application-layer protocols.

Deleted research data objects: The verification of persistence of metadata even when a data set has been deleted (**FsF-A2-01M**), sometimes referred to as ‘tombstoning’, is an important FAIR metric that is virtually impossible to test however during the implementation of tests we found that it is hardly possible to test this at data set level. Handling of deleted data and metadata records strongly depends on policies and procedures at the repository level. For example if these repositories maintain so-called tombstone pages in case a data set has been deleted. However, no machine-interpretable indicator of tombstone status exists to date. We therefore decided to not include this metric for the current assessment implementation.

Interoperability

Knowledge representation language: Metric **FsF-I1-01M** is dealing with the presence of semantic technologies. Making the metadata document available in a knowledge representation language requires the use of appropriate serialisation formats such as RDF, RDFS, OWL. F-UJI verifies the presence of a knowledge representation language by checking if the collected metadata is serialized as JSON-LD or RDFa (Landing Page Content) or e.g. provided via Content Negotiation in one of the serialization formats for RDF (e.g. Turtle, XML, JSON-LD) recognized by the Python library RDFlib¹⁵.

Semantic resources: Regarding semantic resources (**FsF-I1-02M**) we assume that the namespaces of semantic resources available in a metadata document indicate that corresponding terms are also used. We do not consider generic namespaces (e.g., of RDF, RDFS, XSD) but focus on namespaces representing semantic resources such as ontologies, thesauri, and taxonomies. Because unfortunately no complete, authoritative, cross-domain semantic resources registry exists, therefore we collated metadata from two sources, Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV)¹⁶ and Linked Open Data Cloud¹⁷. Deprecated semantic resources are excluded during the process. We regard

¹⁵ <https://github.com/RDFLib>

¹⁶ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

¹⁷ <https://lod-cloud.net/>

this as an interim solution to verify the presence or absence of used semantic resources which probably will be substituted or emended by future projects and initiatives and emerging services such as Fairsharing¹⁸.

Related resources: links to related entities (**FsF-I3-01M**) such as prior version, associated datasets, publications help to understand the broader context of research data objects. Commonly used relation types are listed in the DataCite Metadata Schema (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019) or the Dublin Core terminology. The practical tests make use of relations indicated by PROV-O terms (Moreau et al. 2011) or generic related resources indicated in metadata e.g. in Dublin Core records. In general, machine-readable unique or persistent identifiers are best suited to denote related entities, but the test also accepts the presence of free text expressions of, for example, references.

Reusability

Data content descriptors: To ease processing of data, metadata should include technical properties (file format and size) or content descriptors (measured variables) of a data object. The implementation of **FsF-R1-01MD** therefore verifies the presence of data content descriptors in appropriate fields of metadata records. It further checks if a resource type is given and validates the values of the descriptors against the actual data file. Apache Tika is here used for content analysis. The content descriptors we defined are based on the recommendations (Austin et al. 2019) of the RDA Data Fitness for Use Working Group¹⁹.

Data licence: Users need to know under which conditions the data may be reused, so the metadata should contain an explicit licence statement. Our implementation of metric **FsF-R1.1-01M** therefore checks if a data object's licence is specified using an appropriate metadata field. This test checks if a valid licence identifier (URL) is used but also tries to recognize free text licence strings. For reference, we use the SPDX licence list²⁰ to verify that a standard licence is used.

Provenance: Provenance related metadata (**FsF-R1.2-01M**) depends on data type purpose and application (Herschel, Diestelkämper, and Ben Lahmar 2017) which makes it difficult to define a cross-domain set of provenance properties. Therefore, we focus on provenance information related to data creation following the PROV W3C definition (Groth and Moreau 2013) which is suitable for data on the web in general

¹⁸ <https://fairsharing.org>

¹⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/assessment-data-fitness-use>

²⁰ <https://spdx.org/licenses/>

(Hartig 2009). To distinguish data creation provenance metadata in domain agnostic metadata standards we use existing mappings to the PROV-O ontology (e.g. (Garijo and Eckert 2013)) to capture properties for data sources, data creation or collection date, actors involved in data creation, modification, and versioning information. In addition, we check if data provenance information is accessible in a machine-readable way using specialised vocabularies and ontologies such as PROV-O (Moreau et al. 2011) or PAV (Ciccarese et al. 2013).

Community standards: Developing automated tests to verify the presence of community specific metadata (**FsF-R1.3-01M**) is a challenge since data providers may offer a data object's metadata by methods which are not necessarily linked or connected to a PID or landing page URI. For example, common harvesting protocol endpoints for e.g. OAI-PMH and Catalog Service for the Web (CSW) currently can not be included in most metadata standards. Furthermore, some of these services, especially OAI-PMH, cannot use the same identifier (PID) that was used to publish the object (Huber et al, 2021). An interim solution is to retrieve a data repository ID from DataCite REST API which offers provider identifiers²¹ collected as part of its PID registration service in re3data. We use these provider IDs to retrieve information about metadata access endpoints from registries such as FAIRsharing and re3data.org, and the supported metadata standards listed there. Since this approach is limited to objects registered with PIDs via Datacite, F-UJI accepts service endpoints URI as additional input parameters, verifies that associated domains match each other and uses these interfaces to retrieve domain specific standards. Initially the tool supports OAI-PMH, CSW and SPARQL and compares the namespaces included in all retrieved metadata documents with the namespaces of domain metadata standards listed in the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog²² which we use as an initial reference to identify the 'target community-standard namespace' tuple required for the test.

Community file formats: Some aspects have to be considered when choosing community-appropriate file formats to implement FsF-R1.3-02D: their long-term usability and standardisation as well as discipline specific analytical requirements. In general, long term file formats and open, standard file formats can be regarded as beneficial for the scientific community. The scientific community also needs discipline-specific and multidisciplinary scientific file formats that simplify data analysis workflows. Several databases exist which provide access to a large number of file formats and associated mime types²³ but these registries do not indicate potential

²¹ <https://api.datacite.org/repositories>

²² <https://github.com/rd-alliance/metadata-catalog-v2>

²³ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/>

scientific target user communities. Unfortunately no authoritative registry for scientific file formats yet exists. As an interim solution we curate an extensible controlled list of scientific formats which is available at Github²⁴, which includes associated mime types and scientific target communities. The list was compiled from the Archive Team list of scientific file formats²⁵ and the Wolfram Alpha list of supported scientific file formats²⁶. Our list also includes some generic file formats taken from the Library of Congress Recommended Formats list²⁷. Similarly, we assembled two extensible, controlled lists dedicated to long term and open formats based on the ISO/TR 22299²⁸ digital file format recommendations for long-term storage, the Wikipedia list of open formats²⁹ as well as the openformats.org³⁰ initiative format list. We verify file formats and associated mime types detected within the metadata of a given data set and test if these are recorded in the lists mentioned above to distinguish scientifically recommended file formats such as long term file format, open file format or scientific file format.

1.4 Other work / related activity

During the last years, several FAIR data assessment tools have been developed. An overview on current approaches has been collected by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity WG survey on existing FAIR assessment tools (Bahim, Dekkers, and Wyns 2019), a list of resources and tools is available at the FAIRassist.org website. For the EOSC, during a recent workshop a number of FAIR assessment and certification tools have been presented (Gaiarin Pittonet 2020).

Most existing FAIR assessment tools listed there are supporting the manual, self-assessment of FAIR data carried out through case studies, checklists or questionnaires. For example, the CSIRO 5-star tool³¹ allows self-assessment of data sets. FAIR-Aware is similar and also web based but builds on the above mentioned metrics. The choice of machine based, automatized FAIR assessment tools is limited. A notable solution is the FAIR Evaluation Services³² hosted by fairsharing.org, which assesses data programmatically based on core maturity indicators. FAIRshake³³ is a toolkit that facilitates the manual and automated assessment of different research

²⁴ https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji/blob/master/fuji_server/data/science_formats.json

²⁵ http://justsolve.archiveteam.org/wiki/Scientific_Data_formats

²⁶ <https://reference.wolfram.com/language/guide/ScientificAndMedicalDataFormats.html>

²⁷ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/TOC.html>

²⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/73117.html>

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_open_formats

³⁰ <https://web.archive.org/web/20060215074955/http://www.openformats.org/enShowAll>

³¹ <http://5stardata.csiro.au/>

³² <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd>

³³ <https://fairshake.cloud/>

assets based on existing individuals or a collection of metrics. A computational workflow to perform a semi-automated evaluation of datasets from life sciences repositories was presented by (Ammar et al. 2020). Further, publication and cataloguing services use specific FAIR assessments e.g., DataONE³⁴ or OpenAIRE³⁵ provide validator services to quantitatively evaluate metadata completeness prior to harvesting and ingesting metadata records.

Both tools build on the findings of these works and are in particular influenced by the results of the international RDA FAIR Data Maturity WG as well as to the EOSC FAIR working group. They both represent an attempt to implement the recommendations and theoretical groundwork of these groups in practice and to enable the community to put the FAIR principles into operation.

2. Data Assessment Toolset

2.1 FAIR-Aware

2.1.1 Description

The FAIR-Aware online self-assessment tool (figure 3) aims to raise researchers and data stewards' awareness about the value of making data FAIR before depositing it into a repository. Making data FAIR is still an unclear process for many researchers across various disciplines. To help researchers and data stewards bridge this knowledge gap, FAIR-Aware emphasises educating and raising awareness of FAIR data rather than measuring the extent to which their datasets are FAIR. It promotes FAIRness literacy³⁶ in a practical way and communicates how the FAIR data principles can increase data value and impact. This tool is aimed both at researchers, to take control over their own FAIR knowledge and skill development, as well as at data stewards, who can include this tool in their services for researchers.

³⁴ <https://www.dataone.org/fair/>

³⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/validator/>

³⁶ David, R., Mabile, L., Specht, A., Stryeck, S., Thomsen, M., Yahia, M., ... Alliance – SHaring Reward and Credit (SHARC) Interest Group, T. R. D. (2020). FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), 32. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-032>

The screenshot displays the FAIR-Aware self-assessment tool interface. It is divided into three main sections:

- About you:** A section for user identification with a dropdown for 'Domain' and checkboxes for roles (Researcher, Funder, Policy maker, Publisher, Research support, Other) and organization types (Research infrastructure, Funding Body, Library, Publisher, Industry, University, Research Performing Organisation, Government, Infrastructure).
- FAIR questions:** A series of 10 questions categorized into four groups:
 - FINDABLE:** Questions 1-3 regarding dataset identification and discoverability.
 - ACCESSIBLE:** Questions 4-5 regarding data access and reuse.
 - INTEROPERABLE:** Question 6 regarding metadata description.
 - REUSABLE:** Questions 7-10 regarding provenance, metadata inclusion, community standards, and data deposition.
- Feedback:** A section for user feedback on the tool, including a 'Submit' button and a 'Privacy statement' link.

Figure 3. FAIR-Aware self-assessment tool.

The 10 assessment questions are derived from the FAIRsFAIR object metrics specification (Devaraju et al., 2020)³⁷, and cover all aspects of the FAIR data principles. These questions guide researchers through (meta) data topics such as discovery metadata, licence and provenance information, sustainable file formats and persistent identifiers. Rich guidance and practical examples are provided with each question. After submitting their answers, users receive a “FAIR Awareness” score along with suggestions for making their dataset more FAIR.

3.1.2 Technical implementation of the tool

The FAIR-Aware tool is hosted by DANS³⁸, the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data. DANS will continue hosting the tool after the project ends in February 2022. The tool has been developed in cooperation with PANGEA and the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)³⁹. The application is realised as a static HTML webpage, using Javascript and CSS (Cascading Style Sheets).

³⁷ Devaraju, Anusuriya, Huber, Robert, Mokrane, Mustapha, Herterich, Patricia, Cepinskas, Linas, de Vries, Jerry, ... Angus White. (2020, October 12). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (Version 0.4). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213>

³⁸ <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl>

³⁹ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk>

User responses to questions are stored in the cloud⁴⁰ but no associated personal data is retained to ensure General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR) compliance. The development team collects the answers to monitor the level of awareness of users of the FAIR principles and their intent to comply with these principles. The collected feedback is used to guide future improvements to the tool so it is up to date and relevant for different user groups.

The source code⁴¹ is available online under the MIT License Open Source Software licence⁴² and is customisable to facilitate adoption by other repositories, and as part of FAIRsFAIR engagement and training activities.

2.1.3 Test-bed

Since the successful integration and testing of the beta version in June 2020⁴³, the FAIR-Aware tool has been continuously improved to meet the needs of the users. Importantly, the user satisfaction with the tool has grown significantly. The latest results⁴⁴ demonstrate that 81% of the respondents agree that the tool helped raise their awareness and understanding of the FAIR data principles. This finding reiterates the value of making such support tools available to the research community. In general, the users find the tool clear, informative, and easy to use across different research domains. The users of FAIR-Aware have shared the following feedback with the development team:

“The FAIR principles were not familiar to me at the time when I was trying to get published. The FAIR-Aware tool is informative and easy to use as a point of reference for my further publication career.”

⁴⁰ Firebase Real Time DataBase <https://firebase.google.com/docs/database>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/fair-assessment-tool>

⁴² <https://github.com/FAIRsFAIR/fair-aware/blob/master/LICENSE>

⁴³ Devaraju, A., Mokrane, M., Cepinskas, L., Huber, R., Herterich, P., de Vries, J., Akerman, V., L’Hours, H., Davidson, J. and Diepenbroek, M., 2021. From Conceptualization to Implementation: FAIR Assessment of Research Data Objects. *Data Science Journal*, 20(1), p.4. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2021-004>

⁴⁴ As of 8 June 2021

“I found this tool very useful and clear. I would like to forward it to researchers in my country to bring clear and easy information for them in order to better understand FAIR.”

“Useful guidelines for research fields.”

“A very nice tool with striking simplicity.”

FAIR-Aware users and their needs

FAIR-Aware is being used by a broad range of stakeholders. At the moment of writing this report, 238 users have made use of the tool representing a variety of roles. The majority of the users are researchers (47.8%). Second to them are research support staff (42.6%), followed by other roles (4.3%), policy makers (3.2%), and publishers (2.4%). Funders may also find the tool useful in clarifying the FAIR data principles and translating them into practice, though outreach to these stakeholders is limited to date (0.4%). This will be addressed in the near future during funder-related events and campaigns.

Figure 4. Respondents' roles.

The development of FAIR-Aware has been iterative and continuous. The project team has successfully incorporated extensive user feedback on the metrics as well as the user interface from the testing phase. Earlier user suggestions included providing more

discipline specific and data type examples, elaborating on the level of data access and related legal obligations, and making FAIR-Aware available in other languages. The tool is discipline-agnostic, but the guidance texts will include more domain specific examples to make the information more relevant for individual users. This is a necessary addition considering the diversity of issues or maturity levels in terms of available solutions across different disciplines. In addition, user suggestions also led to the incorporation of ‘willingness to comply’ as a measure in the tool. The project has already addressed these areas in expanding and revising the information tips with additional guidance and examples.

While the technical aspects of the tool are not expected to be further developed except for correcting bugs that might be uncovered and necessary functionalities for wider reuse (a trainer function, a social media share buttons etc.), the guidance tips can/will still evolve until the end of the project.

Awareness of the FAIR data principles

FAIR-Aware users have a high level of awareness about FAIR data practices with an average of 89% on all of the 10 self-assessment questions (see figure 5). Yet, as user feedback shows, there are some knowledge gaps in a number of areas related to these practices.

Figure 5. Awareness indicated by the users.

Based on the latest feedback, users still have some difficulties understanding several aspects of FAIR data (see figure 6). To illustrate, the key issues are mainly related to the use of semantic vocabularies in metadata, community-endorsed metadata, provenance metadata, and digital curation and preservation. The development team is continuously developing and improving the information and guidance to address these areas in the tool.

The tool will be updated based on incoming user feedback and scientific developments to meet the needs of the user base. As a final version of the FAIRsFAIR project, FAIR-Aware will be released in M36. As indicated earlier, FAIR-Aware will be further hosted and maintained by DANS to ensure the sustainability of the tool.

Figure 6. Difficult areas indicated by respondents.

As a response to the users' feedback, the project has included an additional question to the tool measuring the intent of users to comply with a particular aspect of the FAIR data principles ('To what degree do you intend to comply with this?'). Based on the latest results from the tool (see figure 7), it can be observed that there is some variation among users' intent to follow the FAIR data principles. To illustrate, the majority of users (65.5%) are likely to provide discovery metadata of their dataset. This finding suggests that a large share of users understand the importance of metadata in making their datasets findable. In addition, 63.9% of the users are willing to provide information on access control to the metadata of their dataset and 61.8% of the users intend to provide a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier (PID) to their dataset. However, less than half of the users are willing to follow professional digital curation and preservation guidelines (49.6%) and use semantic vocabularies (46.6%).

Based on the above, it can be concluded that a significant number of FAIR-Aware users are willing to embrace the FAIR data principles. However, some of them are less likely to follow several aspects of the FAIR principles, namely professional digital curation and preservation guidelines and use of semantic vocabularies. This may have to do with the users lacking knowledge and availability of ready to use services in these two areas as semantic artefacts so far have been developed in silos and

interoperability between them is a challenge⁴⁵. The development team will address these areas in the information tips with additional guidance and explanation in close collaboration with the FAIRsFAIR task group working on semantic artefacts.

Figure 7. FAIR-Aware users' intent to comply with FAIR topics.

FAIR-Aware in practice

Users start the manual assessment by reading a short introduction about the tool and how to use it. Then they are asked to share some background details, such as their research domain, their role and the type of organisation they currently work at. Once they have finished this part, they are asked to answer ten questions related to the FAIR data principles (see figure 8). Each question contains an information tip marked with an 'i' which provides practical examples and guidance on a specific topic (see figure 8).

⁴⁵ Hugo, Wim, Le Franc, Yann, Coen, Gerard, Parland-von Essen, Jessica, & Bonino, Luiz. (2020). D2.5 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Second Iteration (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4314321>

F

FAIR questions

FINDABLE

1. Are you aware that a dataset should be assigned a globally unique persistent and resolvable identifier when deposited with a data repository?

Yes
 No
2. Are you aware that when you deposit a dataset with a repository, you will need to provide some details (known as discovery metadata) in order to make the data findable, understandable and reusable to others?

Yes
 No
3. Are you aware that the repository providing access to your dataset should make the metadata describing your datasets available in a format readable by machines as well as humans?

Yes
 No

ACCESSIBLE

1. Are you aware that a dataset should be assigned a globally unique persistent and resolvable identifier when deposited with a data repository? ✕

Selected datasets should be assigned a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier (PID) so they can be located unambiguously by humans or machines on the web. Persistent identifiers are maintained and governed so that they remain stable and direct the users to the same relevant object consistently over time. Examples of PIDs include Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the Handle System, identifiers.org, w3id.org and Archival Resource Key (ARK).

Identifiers are normally assigned by data repositories (or other service providers) when data and/or metadata are made available through their services. Repositories ensure that the identifier continues to point to the same data or metadata, according to the specified access terms and conditions. For example, you can search for data repositories providing DOIs on registries such as Re3data [↗](#) or FAIRsharing (see related databases) [↗](#).

It is worth noting here that not all data you produce during your research will need a PID. In general, those that underpin published findings or have longer term value are worth assigning a PID. If in doubt about which data should be allocated a PID, speak to your local research data management support team.

[Want to know more?](#)

Close

Figure 8. Information tips and additional guidance.

Next to each question, users are asked to indicate to what degree they intend to comply with a particular aspect of FAIR data. This question was a suggestion from the user community, and the main objective of it is to check the actual intention of the user to comply with the FAIR data principles.

Yes To what degree do you intend to comply with this?
 No Very likely 5 4 3 2 1 Very unlikely

Yes To what degree do you intend to comply with this?
 No Very likely 5 4 3 2 1 Very unlikely

Yes To what degree do you intend to comply with this?
 No Very likely 5 4 3 2 1 Very unlikely

Figure 9. Intention to comply with the FAIR data principles.

After answering the ten questions, users are invited to share their feedback (optional). The feedback consists of four questions. Question one deals with specific issues covered in the 10 questions. Question two focuses on any missing but relevant aspects in the tool. Questions three and four are dedicated for general feedback to improve the tool and checking if the self-assessment helped the user raise their awareness and understanding of the FAIR data principles.

After submitting their answers, users receive two scores. One of them is a ‘FAIR awareness’ score and another one is a ‘Willingness to comply’ with the FAIR data principles score based on the information they had provided. These scores give a rough estimate to users on their current awareness levels of the FAIR data principles and the intention to comply with them. Along with the scores, users also receive additional guidance focussing on the areas with the low scores. Users can export or print this feedback page together with an overview of their submission. The idea is that users use this learning opportunity to critically reflect on their daily practices with research data and start using the FAIR data principles.

Thank you for your participation!

Awareness:
High (8/10)

Willingness to comply:
Low (27/50)

Guidance:

Based on your answers, you can find the guidance below to improve your awareness on some FAIR issues.

1. Are you aware that a dataset should be assigned a globally unique persistent and resolvable identifier when deposited with a data repository?

Selected datasets should be assigned a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier (PID) so they can be located unambiguously by humans or machines on the web. Persistent identifiers are maintained and governed so that they remain stable and direct the users to the same relevant object consistently over time. Examples of PIDs include Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the Handle System, identifiers.org, w3id.org and Archival Resource Key (ARK).

Identifiers are normally assigned by data repositories (or other service providers) when data and/or metadata are made available through their

Figure 10. Display of a filled in FAIR-Aware self-assessment.

Analysis and use of assessment results

Currently, only the FAIRsFAIR project team can view the submitted results in the FAIR-Aware tool. The team members can download the results from the Firebase database through the tool’s webpage. By downloading the results in a .csv file, they can analyse them using any spreadsheet software. In the coming months, a new functionality will be developed to more effectively facilitate the adoption of FAIR-Aware in external training activities or for other purposes, such as research projects. The functionality will allow trainers to download the results of their trainees. By having an overview of their trainee results, trainers will be able to analyse the results by themselves and tailor their training activities accordingly.

2.2 F-UJI

2.2.1 Description

F-UJI is an open-source tool implementing a REST API to assess the FAIRness of research data at the dataset level based on the FAIR object assessment metrics described above (section 1.2). For each of these metrics, practical tests have been implemented for machine based verification based on existing standards and best practices. Since the FAIR principles have been proposed as “domain-independent, high-level principles that can be applied to a wide range of scholarly outputs” (Wilkinson et al. 2016) we aimed for the broadest possible interdisciplinary application scenario. Therefore, we initially focussed on implementing machine based FAIR assessments verifying domain agnostic web standards and formats commonly used within the scientific community instead of community specifics.

The current version of F-UJI was implemented using Python as a programming language and Swagger to describe the structure of the API as well as to generate the necessary client libraries and API Web GUI. We released the source code under the MIT License Open Source Software licence via Github at <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>. F-UJI⁴⁶ is designed as a REST API standardized according to the OpenAPI specifications⁴⁷.

2.2.2 Technical Implementation

Service implementation and workflow

The F-UJI API provides two methods: the ‘*evaluate*’ method serves to perform all FAIR assessments against given datasets and the ‘*metric*’ method returns a JSON string which documents the FAIR assessment metrics used by the service.

The ‘*evaluate*’ method accepts two main input parameters as illustrated in Figure 11. It expects a mandatory unique identifier (‘*object_identifier*’) of the data object which shall be evaluated. Additionally, users can optionally pass a repository’s metadata provision service (e.g., OAI-PMH, CSW) endpoint URI and type (‘*metadata_service_endpoint*’, ‘*metadata_service_type*’) to the service. This is of interest, because these protocols are commonly used to expose additional metadata for example serialized in community-specific formats. In addition, the service offers the possibility to define (‘*use_datacite*’) if third party services offered by DataCite such as the JSON content

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>

⁴⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/metadata-standards-catalog-working-group.html>

negotiation or re3data registry information shall be used during an evaluation or not. The 'test_debug' parameter serves to suppress debug messages, it is recommended to leave the default setting which includes those verbose messages.

Figure 11. Screenshot of the Swagger GUI illustrating the expected input parameters for the 'evaluate' method of the REST API

The workflow the tool follows during each assessment is illustrated in Fig. 12. Initially, F-UJI checks the syntax of the identifier provided using the Python library 'IDutils'⁴⁸ to identify standard identifier schemes utilizing regular expressions to match common identifier patterns and syntax. In addition, the tool recognizes identifiers.org compliant identifiers and associated schemes. It further attempts to transform the given identifier into an actionable representation and verifies if this representation resolves to a landing page.

Using both, landing page URI as well as the identifier URI, F-UJI retrieves a defined set of metadata of the assessed data required for the subsequent assessment of all FAIR metrics. F-UJI uses the above-mentioned mechanisms to retrieve metadata via 'structured data', 'content negotiation' or 'typed or Signposting links'.

F-UJI adheres to existing web standards and utilises external registries and resources. Dedicated parsers have been implemented to retrieve metadata represented in commonly used, domain agnostic standards Dublin Core, schema.org/Dataset, DataCite, and DCAT-2 in appropriate formats (XML, RDF, or JSON) or feeds such as OAI-ORE, atom or GeoRSS. For RDF documents we utilize the RDFLib Python package which supports a variety of formats such as Turtle, JSON-LD or RDF/XML. F-UJI also provides XPath mappings to parse some of the most frequently used

⁴⁸ <https://idutils.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

metadata standards from various domains such as DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) Codebook, ISO 19115: Geographic information-Metadate expressed as ISO 19139 XML, Ecological Modelling Language (EML), Dublin Core Schema XML, DataCite Schema XML as well as Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS (METS)) XML. It further recognizes metadata expressed as microdata⁴⁹ or RDFa (Adida et al. 2015), formats.

F-UJI compiles the metadata provided via these formats and transforms this metadata into an internal data structure (Python dictionary). This metadata is used to perform the individual FAIR tests according to the FAIRsFAIR metric in the following steps as described above. In addition, all namespaces and schema URIs identified within the above-mentioned metadata sources are collected and stored by F-UJI to verify domain specific standards and to assess if semantic resources are used.

Figure 12. Schematic workflow of F-UJI's metadata collection. Taking a PID as a starting point, F-UJI collects embedded metadata from the landing page and performs content negotiation using PID URL as well as landing page URL to retrieve additional or alternative metadata formats. Further typed links are followed to collect metadata from dedicated metadata documents. Collected metadata is transformed into an internal data structure.

Beneath metadata related tests as described above and listed in table 1, F-UJI also attempts to verify the actual data (data object, downloadable file) against given metadata. The tool first collates object's content identifiers (i.e., downloadable file

⁴⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/microdata/>

URIs) given within the metadata as well as data content identifiers offered via Signposting links. Further, the tool verifies if a valid data object's resource type is given using controlled vocabularies. Apache Tika is used to verify the data content descriptors (e.g., data format, size, measured variables) specified in the metadata against the actual data deposited. This step also includes the verification of given measured variables within the data object content.

FAIR-enabling services

F-UJI is using several FAIR-enabling services, provided either by the data repository itself or by third parties. Such services are used to validate metadata standards and terminologies used against relevant or authoritative resources, such as the SPDX License List, the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog⁵⁰, and Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV)⁵¹, and Linked Open Data Cloud⁵². Further, F-UJI is using third-party services to collect metadata and data object context information. For example, DataCite offers metadata of data objects in various formats such as JSON-LD and XML via content negotiation on the PID URL. In addition, domain-specific metadata offerings are identified using metadata harvesting protocol services implemented by the data provider such as OAI-PMH ('ListMetadataFormats' request) or OGC CSW ('GetCapabilities' request). In case there is no standard metadata endpoint given as part of the object's assessment request F-UJI tries to discover existing endpoints using the re3data API⁵³. This process is using a previously identified (using the DOI) DataCite repository identifier which was supplied by the repository when registering the object with a PID through DataCite.

⁵⁰ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

⁵¹ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

⁵² <https://lod-cloud.net/>

⁵³ <https://www.re3data.org/api/doc>

Figure 13. Screenshot of the web based client front-end of F-UJI showing the entry page as well the generated graphical output of the FAIR assessment report.

Additional, appropriate FAIR-enabling services including authoritative and curated registries, would strongly support automated FAIR data assessment tools. FAIR-enabling services should be open, well-governed and accessible in a standard way. Some services already exist, but do not fully address the FAIR assessment requirements such as machine readability or discipline specificity. For example, authoritative lists of persistent identifier systems, community specific metadata standards and communication protocols are missing or still incomplete. Fortunately, promising approaches currently emerge such as the FAIRsharing (<https://www.fairsharing.org>) initiative and its associated registry. Going forward, services can make use of the FAIR assessment framework for data services developed by other FAIRsFAIR task groups to highlight how FAIR-enabling they are.⁵⁴

Using F-UJI

F-UJI is accessible in several ways. First, the source code has been made available via Github at <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji> from where interested parties may download, install and run a F-UJI instance on their own servers, it is also possible to run F-UJI in a (Docker) container. Additionally, we have implemented a simple web demo client which is available at <https://www.f-uji.net> which can be used for quick FAIR checks on individual data sets. After the release of the web client some

⁵⁴ A final version of the framework will be published as part of D2.7 Framework for assessing FAIR services due in August 2021. An interim version is available at Koers, Hylke, Herterich, Patricia, Hooft, Rob, Gruenpeter, Morane, Aalto, Tero, & Ramezani, Sara. (2021, May 19). Basic framework on FAIRness of services - iteration 3 (Version 3). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4771937>

months ago, about 3000 individual assessments have been performed using the web demo client. The web demo client also allows storing individual assessments thus sharing saved assessments within the community. It further provides an exemplary implementation of the badge system proposed in this document.

2.2.3 Test-bed

Both F-UJI and FAIRsFAIR metrics have been extensively tested and continuously improved in an iterative process. Six trustworthy data repositories, all CoreTrustSeal⁵⁵ certified, were selected to pilot the FAIR assessment of published data objects. We initially tested the service with approximately 500 randomly selected data objects from these repositories.

Data Repository	Subject Areas	Repository Link
PANGAEA	Earth and Environmental Sciences	https://pangaea.de/
CSIRO Data Access Portal	Multiple disciplines	https://data.csiro.au/collections
DataverseNO	Multiple disciplines	https://dataverse.no/
WDCC CERA	Earth System Science	https://cera-www.dkrz.de/
Phaidra-Italy	Cultural Heritage	https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/

Table 2. Selected pilot data repositories

The testing and evaluation of the FAIR assessment was accompanied by an intensive consultation process. Based on the results of this advisory process, we provided the repositories with detailed recommendations for improving the FAIRness of the data objects via a FAIR assessment report. During a second round of evaluation, the progress of FAIRness was verified using the same datasets. Using the numerical scoring system described in the next section, this could be measured and verified very easily.

⁵⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/certified-repositories/>

Figure 14. FAIR scores of data objects by principle determined during the first iteration

As a result, a significant increase in FAIRness was achieved for all participating data providers that implemented the improvement recommendations. In turn, the knowledge gained during the pilots was used to improve the quality of the F-UJI FAIR assessment software, for example concerning the metadata recognition rates, and to eliminate minor bugs.

Figure 15. FAIR scores of the same data objects by principle determined during the second iteration

Overall, the five repositories evaluated showed a significant improvement in FAIRness. On the basis of the 2500 datasets tested, for example, an improvement was achieved in the area of findability for more than 1000 datasets, and an improvement in accessibility was determined for around 1500 datasets. Significant increases in reusability and interoperability were found in well over 1500 data sets.

3. Badging

3.1 Background, previous work

Digital badges are a very common way of marking certain capabilities or achievements in a conspicuous and visually appealing way on websites. In the meantime, digital badges have conquered large parts of the Internet and can be seen in all kinds of contexts. Here, badges serve to make qualities and characteristics of online resources quickly and transparently detectable for users. Using standardised ‘Open Badges’⁵⁶ it further is possible to verify badges awarded by a trusted issuer. In the commercial sector, for example, they are used to mark the trustworthiness of online stores or to visualize ratings of services and products of all kinds. In the scientific field, prominent examples are altmetric⁵⁷ labels or badges that indicate that a DOI exists for a resource. The Center for Open Science⁵⁸ provides badges to indicate open practices in scientific articles. It is well documented that digital badges may lead to an increase in the open availability of supporting materials in scientific publications and are motivating researchers to share data (Baker 2016; Kidwell et al. 2016). Consequently, badges are ideally suited to illustrate the FAIRness of data sets and may serve to increase the availability of FAIR data in general. The need for FAIR badges for transparent labeling of FAIR datasets was recently expressed by Mark Hahnel (Fig. 16), the founder of Figshare which nicely illustrates the potentially broad uptake of an appropriate badging schema.

⁵⁶ <https://openbadges.org/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.altmetric.com/products/altmetric-badges/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.cos.io/>

Figure 16. Screenshot of a tweet by Mark Hahnel sent on 2 March 2021, source: <https://twitter.com/MarkHahnel/status/1366715758403805187>

Soon after the FAIR principles were published, there was discussion about what a measure of FAIRness might look like and how this could be used for quality labeling of datasets and repositories. Early proposals were based on the 'five star linked open data' concept proposed by (Berners-Lee 2006), providing a star scale from one to five for the quality of linked open data. (Doorn and Dillo 2017) attempted to apply this scale to the FAIRness of data and proposed to assess each FAIR principle individually using this scale and display this on a badge (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Five star badging scheme as proposed by Doorn & Dillo (2017)

This has been taken up and implemented, for example, by (Cox and Yu 2018) for the implementation of their CSIRO 5 star rating tool. A verbose scale, also based on 5 levels, was proposed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG to indicate progress in the implementation of FAIR. The group proposed the visualization of FAIR measurements using this scale as a spider or radar chart. The 'turning FAIR into reality' report (Collins et al. 2018) describes badges as suitable for marking FAIR

achievements and mentions star labels as well as donut-like badges as used by altmetric indicating a numerical score.

3.2 Scoring system

Both methods, star ratings as well as numerical scores are well suited to express achievements. The result of each assessment against the FAIRsFAIR metric given in table 1 is given by F-UJI in various ways which could be used to indicate FAIRness for a given data set. Initially, we considered a pass/fail result for each metric to be appropriate, similarly to how also other FAIR assessment tools behave such as the FAIR Evaluation Services⁵⁹. Furthermore, we defined a scoring system that establishes achievable points for each metric. These points for each metric are explained in the appendix A. The advantage of this scoring system is that it provides a very easy-to-understand end result for a FAIR assessment, which can also be used to make progress measurable. This has been used extensively, for example, in our collaboration with the EOSC-Nordic project and for the pilot assessments and associated FAIR consulting process. Recently, we added a simplified scoring system to indicate FAIR compliance or maturity levels as described in the section dealing with the badging scheme. This scheme is inspired by the FAIRsFAIR CMMI-based⁶⁰ three tiers (initial, managed, defined) proposed for CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling repositories (L'Hours et al. 2021). We have adopted the therein defined three tiers (initial, managed, defined) but due to the different scope renamed them and included level 0 (undefined). These compliance levels have been adapted for the scope of F-UJI as: incomplete (0), initial (1), moderate (2) and advanced (3).

For research data objects, FAIR compliance levels are calculated by F-UJI as follows: Based on the received compliance level for each metric, a maturity level for each FAIR principle is calculated. In case at least one metric of a given principle has reached level 'initial', the corresponding principle cannot have a lower level even if all other metrics are scored lower thus is considered to have reached the 'initial' level. All levels above 'initial' are calculated as the rounded mean of all metrics scores for a given principle. The overall F-UJI FAIR level for a given research data object would analogously be calculated as a rounded mean of all principle scores.

⁵⁹ <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/>

⁶⁰ <https://cmmiinstitute.com/cmml>

3.3 Badge graphics, design

Basically, there are two major design trends as far as the graphic design of badges is concerned. One is the traditional round or polygonal badge, which is very common for marking training skills and is mostly offered by open badge services. In addition, simple rectangular badges are very common in the software community and are used on a large scale, for example in Github, to indicate code quality. The latter is an approach that allows to provide attractive badges without much graphical design effort, which are also well suited for embedding in web pages, as they do not consume much space and fit there almost everywhere. As a pragmatic approach we therefore decided to use such a simple design pattern and are following the shields.io design guidelines⁶¹. Similar badge designs are currently considered for indication of FAIR levels for software⁶² which follow the recommendations for FAIR software (Martinez-Ortiz et al. 2020).

Share FAIR Assessment Results

The Circum-Arctic Sediment Carbon Database — Gridded carbon, nitrogen and isotope data in surface sediments of the Arctic Ocean

Available badges:

Style:	Badge:	Embed:
flat		<code></code>
plastic		<code></code>
flat-square		<code></code>
for-the-badge		<code></code>

Figure 18. Screenshot of the draft web page offering HTML source code which can be used to embed F-UJI FAIR badges in any website.

Following the above mentioned design specifications, we provide badges in different designs, each of them is encoded in SVG which is containing embedded metadata following the Open Badge standard specification⁶³. To create a badge, a given F-UJI assessment has to be saved using the web client available at <https://www.f-uji.net>

⁶¹ <https://github.com/badges/shields/blob/master/spec/SPECIFICATION.md>

⁶² <https://github.com/fair-software/howfairis-livetest>

⁶³ Open Badges Technical Specification V 2.0 : <https://www.imsglobal.org/sites/default/files/Badges/OBv2p0Final/index.html>

which then offers a link to available badges (Fig. 18) . The web page further offers HTML code snippets which can be used to embed F-UJI badges in any website.

The use cases outlined in the introduction (Fig. 1) as well as in appendix B of this report provide an overview of how these badges can be used by a variety of stakeholders in their systems going forward. Especially for badges assigned by repositories, a network of Trusted Digital Repositories (for example aligned with CoreTrustSeal⁶⁴) could play a role in tailoring them to their use cases and define any further development and governance around decision making.

While an automated assessment tool can help with regular checks of the datasets, it was highlighted that training will be required. The training will need to be aimed towards researchers that use the services so they understand how their actions impact the FAIRness of their datasets and which functionalities of the service could help them do so. Furthermore, data curators working for the services need to be trained to support end-users and any aspects of FAIRness checking that an automated tool might not capture.

“It’s like a driving instructor. They are allowed to pass things, you know, they’re allowed to grant FAIR badges. But it’s not the car company giving you FAIR. It’s not the car company saying here’s a car, and we’ll give you a driver’s licence. It’s: here’s a car, you can pass your driver’s licence using this because it passed its MOT and it’s all the level that it’s safe to drive on the roads. We need the FAIR data equivalent of driving instructors”.(M. Hahnel)

4. Impact and adoption

4.1 Impact

F-UJI has been made publicly available as Open Source via the Github platform. It is licenced under an inclusive MIT license which allows a broad range of applications including commercial use. Through this openness we want to achieve the broadest possible community support, which will contribute significantly to the sustainability of the tool. Ideally, in the near future, F-UJI is used, maintained and continuously improved by an active user and developer community. As an indicator for community uptake the number of Github forks can be useful. As of June 2021, there are twelve forks created by different communities that are testing the tool or already using it. This

⁶⁴ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/requirements/>

community includes some important EOSC players (e.g. EOSC-Nordic, EOSC-Synergy and ARCHIVER) which are actively contributing via the GitHub issue ticket system.

At the national level, the German NFDI4Chem has contributed a remarkable, dedicated R library for F-UJI which is available at <https://github.com/NFDI4Chem/rfuji> indicating both community support for, as well as, significance of F-UJI.

Both, FAIR-Aware as well as F-UJI have been presented during several conferences and workshops. Dedicated F-UJI presentations have been given during e.g. AGU2020, EGU2021, FAIR convergence symposium and during several co-organized EOSC-Nordic - GOFAIR FAIRification workshops.

F-UJI's GitHub repository additionally was linked to Zenodo which allows to assign a DOI to the software thus enabling citability of the product: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4063720>. By now, two scientific publications (Devaraju et al. 2021; Huber et al. 2021) on F-UJI and FAIR-Aware have been published which illustrate the use of these tools in practice.

Detailed information regarding the sustainability plans for both tools will be given in deliverable D1.6 (Sustainability Plan). In summary, in the medium term, the continuous maintenance for both tools beyond the project duration is ensured by the current developer institutions. UniHB will maintain F-UJI code and coordinate future developments and will continue to make the tool available via the internet. FAIR-Aware is currently hosted by DANS which runs the tool at a dedicated subdomain. DANS will continue to do so after the completion of the FAIRsFAIR project. It is further aimed at the long term to establish the tools as a core part of the EOSC FAIR ecosystem thus, sharing sustainability efforts with the EOSC infrastructure.

Promotion of FAIR-Aware

Since June 2020, the FAIRsFAIR team has presented and demonstrated the FAIR-Aware tool at a dozen different events in Europe and beyond. These events ranged from national conferences and workshops, such as the Dutch Data Prize Awards ceremony in November 2020⁶⁵, the FAIRsFAIR National Roadshows⁶⁶ to regional conferences, for example, NWO Life 2021⁶⁷. FAIR-Aware was presented to global audiences as well. The project team presented the tool at the CODATA &

⁶⁵ Dutch Data Prize <https://www.rd-alliance.org/dutch-data-prize-together-we-share>

⁶⁶ FAIRsFAIR Roadshow series: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/fairsfair-national-roadshow-series>

⁶⁷ NWO Life2021: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818061>

GFISCO FAIR Convergence Symposium in December 2020⁶⁸, the Open Repositories conferences in June 2020⁶⁹ and 2021⁷⁰, and at the EOSC Symposium 2021⁷¹ and SSHOC Bootcamp held as part of the IASSIST 2021 Global Virtual Pre-Conference in June 2021⁷². The main objective of participating in these and other events was to showcase the practical relevance of the tool, to promote its use among researchers, data stewards and other data professionals, and to raise awareness of the importance of the FAIR data principles. During the SSHOC IASSIST Bootcamp, participants worked to identify potential uses for FAIR-Aware in delivering training.

Thanks to the attendance of these events and related promotional activities, such as news articles⁷³, newsletters⁷⁴, and a demo video⁷⁵, the user community of the tool has grown significantly. Since the beta testing phase in June 2020 with 49 external reviewers, the current number of users stands at almost 240⁷⁶. In addition, the development team has received outstanding feedback and suggestions for future versions of the tool. Worth noting, the trainer community in the research data management domain has also shown a lot of interest in the tool at the IASSIST 2021 Global Virtual Pre-Conference. During a two-day virtual bootcamp around 50 trainers from around the world tested the tool and brainstormed creative ways to reuse it in their training activities. Their generous feedback and ideas will be used in improving the tool and developing training materials to support FAIR data practices in the research community.

4.2 Adoption stories

Expanding the reach of existing users

⁶⁸ FAIR Convergence Symposium: <https://conference.codata.org/FAIRconvergence2020/sessions/219/>

⁶⁹ Open Repositories 2020: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3871523>

⁷⁰ Open Repositories 2021: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4913179>

⁷¹ EOSC Symposium 2021: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-symposium-2021-programme>

⁷² SSHOC Bootcamp:

<https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/sshoc-open-science-and-research-data-management-train-trainer-bootcamp-iassist-pre-conference>

⁷³ See for example, <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>;

<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/current/fairsfair-empowers-researchers-to-become-fair-aware>;

<https://dans.knaw.nl/en/current/news/are-you-fair-aware-a-new-tool-to-make-your-data-fair>

⁷⁴

<https://mailchi.mp/727bbe2ccd61/fairsfair-newsletter-n8-new-fair-data-management-tools-survey-outcomes-and-recommendations-upcoming-events>

⁷⁵ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/current/make-your-data-fair-in-10-easy-steps>

⁷⁶ These statistics were current on 8 June 2021.

Active participation at FAIR related events and initiatives has also brought the project team in touch with enthusiastic data professionals in France. These data professionals have kindly volunteered to translate the FAIR-Aware tool into French, expanding the reach of the scientific community in French-speaking countries. Justine Ancelin-Fabre from the National School of Palaeography and Archival Studies at the URFIST de Paris and Luc Decker from the DataSuds repository of the French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD) have translated the tool with assistance of the project team. Thanks to this successful collaboration, an agreement was made with the Institute of Scientific and Technical Information (INIST), which will host the tool on the DoRANum portal⁷⁷. The DoRANum portal offers a range of different learning resources to support the scientific community in managing and sharing their data. By offering the French version of the FAIR-Aware tool on an already existing and widely used portal, the project will be able to ensure the maintenance and sustainability of the French version of the tool after the project has been concluded in February 2022.

Figure 19. New logo of the French version of FAIR-Aware.

The above example of close collaboration with different stakeholder groups demonstrates the importance of the existence and development of learning tools, such as FAIR-Aware. The project team anticipates other countries and organisations committed to FAIR data practices to follow the lead in integrating the tool into their learning portals, programmes and training curricula.

Similarly, a considerable number of stakeholders became aware of F-UJI. Besides the above described pilot assessments, F-UJI has become a valuable resource to identify potential FAIR improvements for a number of projects and initiatives. An active and mutually beneficial collaboration has been established with the EOSC-Nordic team which is using F-UJI to monitor and improve FAIRness of Nordic data repositories. We have been approached by several other initiatives at the European level such as the ARCHIVER project, EOSC-Synergy and CESSDA. Further, we have been contacted by research infrastructures ICOS and ENVRI-FAIR partners aiming to use F-UJI for internal FAIR assessments. We have conducted detailed FAIR assessments following the proven iterative consultation process as described above to assess several thousand data sets from UKDATA (CESSDA), ARCHIVER and DataverseNL. We are

⁷⁷ <https://doranum.fr/enjeux-benefices/outil-fair-aware/>

currently performing additional FAIR consultations together with teams from the Archeology Data Service⁷⁸. At the national level we have been contacted by the Belgium ECOOM research data portal as well as the German NFDI4Chemistry and we started cooperating with the NFDI4Biodiversity. We have been contacted by EMBRAPA, the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation, the Spanish DataUse project, the Danish Geological Survey (GEUS) and several Universities and research institutions individually (Ugent, Universität Oldenburg, University of Iowa, CNR Italy, Korean Institute of Science and Technology Information) all of them were interested in learning more about the tool and in testing it. The International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) has contacted which helped to understand related disciplinary data offerings. Further, we have been approached by scientific publishers and service providers Elsevier and Figshare (see above). In summary, we have seen an impressive interest in automated FAIR assessments from a wide range of stakeholders over the last few months. All of them provided valuable comments and feedback which helped to significantly improve F-UJI.

FAIR-Aware has also been made part of a new online course developed in the EOSC-Synergy project.⁷⁹ In the module on FAIR principles, course participants will be using FAIR-Aware to test their awareness of and build new knowledge on the FAIR aspects of data. The tool development team aims to make the tool available to different stakeholder groups across Europe and beyond. The integration of the tool in this introductory course is yet another example of such collaborative efforts.

FAIR-Aware has also been adopted for use in a number of FAIRsFAIR's Data Stewardship training activities⁸⁰. Participants of these three day training sessions are assigned homework to review the FAIR-Aware tool and asked to consider which aspects they feel confident about supporting and to identify those topics where additional training or guidance would be needed. Participants share their views using a Menti poll and there is an opportunity to discuss the outcomes. A key aim of these sessions is to encourage participants to consider how they might fill some of the identified knowledge gaps by leveraging expertise that may exist across their institution, through the reuse of openly available guidance and training resources, and/or by leveraging the knowledge of their peers. Below (Fig. 20) is an example of a Menti poll and the results. Similar exercises based on FAIR-Aware will be carried out for the remainder of the FAIRsFAIR data stewardship training programme in 2021.

⁷⁸ <https://www.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

⁷⁹ See 'Bringing synergy to better data management and research in Europe', <https://bit.ly/3zSqWrN>

⁸⁰ <https://fairsfair.eu/events/training>

Which of these FAIR Aware question sets are you most confident about providing training and advice on? (0 = not confident, 10 =very confident)

 Mentimeter

Figure 20. Example of Menti feedback on FAIR-Aware from a FAIRsFAIR's Data Stewardship training session in June 2021.

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Appendix A - Metric Specification v.0.5 (draft)

Globally Unique Identifier

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-F1-01D												
Metric Name	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.												
Description	A data object may be assigned with a globally unique identifier such that it can be referenced unambiguously by humans or machines. Globally unique means an identifier should be associated with only one resource at any time. Examples of unique identifiers of data are Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI) ⁸¹ , Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) such as URL and URN, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the Handle System, identifiers.org, w3id.org and Archival Resource Key (ARK). A data repository may assign a globally unique identifier to your data or metadata when you publish and make it available through its curation service.												
Background	While today most identifiers can be represented as actionable URLs still some non-actionable identifiers may in be in use which are globally unique such as UUID (Philipson, 2017; doi:10.3233/DS-190024)												
FAIR Principle	F1. (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • List of globally unique identifier schemes 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Identifier is not resolvable but follows an UUID or HASH type syntax</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (URL, IRI)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Identifier is not resolvable but follows an UUID or HASH type syntax	0.5	2			3	Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (URL, IRI)	1
level	test	score											
1	Identifier is not resolvable but follows an UUID or HASH type syntax	0.5											
2													
3	Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (URL, IRI)	1											
Method	Check if the identifier is specified based on a globally unique identifier scheme.												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifiers compiled by FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/?q=&selected_facets=type_exact:identifier%20schema • A list of Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) schemes, available in different formats, https://www.iana.org/assignments/uri-schemes/uri-schemes.xhtml#uri-schemes-1 • Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) Generic Syntax (RFC 3986), https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986 													

⁸¹ IRI is a generalization of URI that permits Universal Character Set.

Persistent Identifier

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-F1-02D												
Metric Name	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.												
Description	In this specification, we make a distinction between the uniqueness and persistence of an identifier. An HTTP URL (the address of a given unique resource on the web) is globally unique, but may not be persistent as the URL of data may be not accessible (link rot problem) or the data available under the original URL may be changed (content drift problem). Identifiers based on, e.g., the Handle System, DOI, ARK are both globally unique and persistent. They are maintained and governed such that they remain stable and resolvable for the long term. The persistent identifier (PID) of a data object may be resolved (point) to a landing page with metadata containing further information on how to access the data content, in some cases a downloadable artefact, or none if the data or repository is no longer maintained. Therefore, ensuring persistence is a shared responsibility between a PID service provider (e.g., datacite) and its clients (e.g., data repositories). For example, the DOI system guarantees the persistence of its identifiers through its social (e.g., policy) and technical infrastructures, whereas a data provider ensures the availability of the resource (e.g., landing page, downloadable artefact) associated with the identifier.												
Background	The EOSC PID policy requires a PID to be globally unique, persistent, and resolvable (Valle et al., 2020). No authoritative list or registry of persistent identifiers yet exists, but the DataCite identifier type vocabulary (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019) is listing most common PID types. These can be used except identifiers exclusively used for print products and physical entities (e.g., ISBN, EAN, ROR). In addition, identifiers listed in identifiers.org can be used to complement the controlled list.												
FAIR Principle	F1. (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers												
CoreTrustSeal alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Landing page of the identifier • List of commonly accepted persistent identifiers for data 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Persistent identifier is resolvable (landing page can be reached)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0.5	2			3	Persistent identifier is resolvable (landing page can be reached)	1
level	test	score											
1	Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0.5											
2													
3	Persistent identifier is resolvable (landing page can be reached)	1											
Method	Check if the data identifier specified is based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme and syntax, and it resolves to a landing page with metadata containing further information on how to access the data object. Note that this assessment method follows the current best practice to have a PID resolve to a landing page instead of its actual content.												

COMMENTS

Related Resources

- A wiki entry on persistent identifier, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persistent_identifier
- Generic PID definitions, Initial Persistent Identifier Policy for the EOSC, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3574202>
- FREYA Deliverable 3.1 (Survey of Current PID Services Landscape), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324295>
- FREYA Deliverable 2.1 PID Resolution Services Best Practices, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324299>

Known Limitations/Constraints

- The assessment verifies the resolvability of the specified identifier to a landing page, but a PID may resolve to a data file or a web service response.
- A registry of persistent identifiers should provide the list of identifiers as well as associated policy documents for ensuring persistence that may be periodically reviewed and updated. If a policy document is issued with a validity period, this should be captured by the registry.
- A PID service provider may periodically check if an identifier within its registry is resolvable (e.g., <https://support.datacite.org/docs/link-checker>). While the PID itself may be persistent, it may not resolve to a downloadable artefact if the data or repository is no longer maintained.

Descriptive Core Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F2-01M
Metric Name	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
Description	Metadata is descriptive information about a data object. Since the metadata required differs depending on the users and their applications, this metric focuses on core metadata. The core metadata is the minimum descriptive information required to enable data finding, including citation which makes it easier to find data. We determine the required metadata based on common data citation guidelines (e.g., DataCite, ESIP, and IASSIST), and metadata recommendations for data discovery (e.g., EOSC Datasets Minimum Information (EDMI), DataCite Metadata Schema, W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices and Data Catalog Vocabulary).

	This metric focuses on domain-agnostic core metadata. Domain or discipline-specific metadata specifications are covered under metric FsF-R1.3-01M . A repository should adopt a schema that includes properties of core metadata, whereas data authors should take the responsibility of providing core metadata.													
Background	<p>Following data citation guidelines (Data Citation Synthesis Group, 2014, Ball & Duke, 2015; Mooney & Newton, 2012 and Fenner et al., 2019) metadata properties necessary for proper data citation are: <i>creator, title, publication date, publisher, and identifier</i>.</p> <p>In addition, abstract or summary and keywords are essential to enable discoverability and the indication of a resource type is necessary to distinguish research data objects from other digital objects (Fenner et al., 2019).</p> <p>The resulting set of core descriptive metadata elements (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) aligns well with existing recommendations for data discovery and core metadata definition (Asmi et al., 2017, DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019, Loscio et al., 2017 and Albertoni et al., 2020). This set of metadata elements is present in most domain agnostic metadata standards such as Dublin Core, DCAT-2, schema.org/Dataset, and DataCite schema.</p>													
FAIR Principle	F2. Data are described with rich metadata													
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation													
ASSESSMENT														
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 													
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Some metadata has been made available via common web methods(embedded, typed links, content negotiation)</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Core data citation metadata is available</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Core descriptive metadata is available</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Some metadata has been made available via common web methods(embedded, typed links, content negotiation)	0.5	2	Core data citation metadata is available	1	3	Core descriptive metadata is available	2	
level	test	score												
1	Some metadata has been made available via common web methods(embedded, typed links, content negotiation)	0.5												
2	Core data citation metadata is available	1												
3	Core descriptive metadata is available	2												
Method	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Parse or retrieve core metadata, e.g., through one or more options below, combine the results and then verify presence/absence of the core elements in the metadata.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured data embedded in the landing page of the identifier (e.g., Schema.org, Dublin Core and OpenGraph meta tags) • Typed Links in the HTTP Link header; for more information, see https://signposting.org/conventions/ • Content negotiation (including external negotiation services offered by PID providers) <p>Check if metadata has to be made available via common methods at all. Check if data citation metadata is available. Check if core descriptive metadata is available.</p>													
COMMENTS														

Related Resources

- Examples of metadata recommendations:
 - EOSC EDMI metadata properties, <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>
 - W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices, <https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#metadata>
 - W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary, <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>
- Sites that provide a list of metadata standards:
 - FAIRsharing, <https://fairsharing.org/standards/>
 - RDA Metadata Directory (General Research Data Standards), <https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/subjects/general.html>
- Examples of domain agnostic metadata standards for describing research data:
 - Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) Metadata Terms, <https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#bib-DCTERMS>
 - DataCite Metadata Schema, <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>
 - Schema.org, <https://schema.org/Dataset>
 - Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

Known Limitations/Constraints

- The assessment assumes that the identifier resolves to a landing page (e.g., html) that contains the metadata of the data. Landing page may not necessarily be an html page.
- Data providers may use different standards to expose the metadata of their data.
- The metadata records maintained by a data provider might not be accessible, due to, e.g., broken link of the landing page, proprietary metadata standard used, and restricted metadata.

Inclusion of Data Identifier in Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION						
Metric Identifier	FsF-F3-01M						
Metric Name	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.						
Description	The metadata should explicitly specify the identifier of the data (content) such that users can discover and access the data through the metadata. If the identifier specified is persistent and points to a landing page, the data identifier and links to download the data content should be taken into account in the assessment.						
FAIR Principle	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe						
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation						
ASSESSMENT							
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata 						
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score			
level	test	score					

	1	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)	0.5
	2		
	3	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	1
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Check if the identifier (link) to access data content is included in the metadata (e.g., use the metadata elements 'schema:Distribution', 'foaf:isPrimaryTopicOf' or Typed Links), and test if the content identifier is active. 		
COMMENTS			
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Signposting the Scholarly Web, https://signposting.org/conventions/ FAIR Signposting Profile, https://signposting.org/FAIR/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A metadata standard may not support any element or include multiple elements through which a data identifier may be specified. Different practices of associating data with its metadata should be handled as part of the assessment: Data is assigned with an identifier that resolves to a page that contains metadata of the data. The metadata may contain the identifier and a URL to access the data (contents). In this case, the access URL should be tested. Data and metadata are assigned with separate identifiers. Therefore, the data identifier should be tested. 			

Searchable Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F4-01M
Metric Name	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.
Description	This metric refers to ways through which the metadata of data is exposed or provided in a standard and machine-readable format. Assessing this metric will require an understanding of the capabilities offered by the data repository used to host the data. Metadata may be available through multiple endpoints. For example, if data is hosted by a repository, the repository may disseminate its metadata through a metadata harvesting protocol (e.g., via OAI-PMH) and/or a web service. Metadata may also be embedded as structured data on a data page for use by web search engines such as Google and Bing or be available as linked (open) data.
FAIR Principle	F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation														
ASSESSMENT															
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoint (if it is not included in the metadata or landing page of the identifier) 														
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1			2	Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)	1	3	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa)	2		
level	test	score													
1															
2	Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)	1													
3	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa)	2													
Assessment	<p>The following methods may be applied to determine if metadata of the data is accessible programmatically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check if the metadata provision endpoint returns metadata records based on a request using the data identifier (see comment* below) • Check if search engine friendly structured data is embedded in the data landing page with a proper resource type, e.g., schema.org representation of type 'Dataset' or 'Collection'. 														
COMMENTS															
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google reference documentation on representing structured data of Dataset, https://developers.google.com/search/docs/data-types/dataset <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • *Data providers may expose their metadata through different ways, e.g., OAI-PMH, REST API using JSONAPI specification, and Catalog Service for the Web (CSW). Their endpoints (URLs) should be machine discoverable and accessible. The metadata access endpoints of a repository can be found through FAIRsharing and re3data. However, at present, it is not possible to programmatically discover the metadata endpoints of a repository based on a data identifier, unless they are explicitly specified in the metadata or the landing page of the data. Mapping the client ids from DataCite's PID service to re3data identifiers is in progress and might provide a starting point for the assessment. • Structured data may be provided in different formats, JSON-LD, RDFa or Microdata. The variety of formats should be handled as part of the assessment. • The assessment only verifies if structured data is present on the data landing page with a proper type (e.g., Dataset or Collection). Embedding structured data does not guarantee that the data will be present on search results. To verify that the data is findable through a web search engine, we should perform a search through the search engine API based on the data identifier and its descriptive metadata (e.g., title, author). However, most of the web search engine APIs (e.g., Google Custom Search, Bing Web Search API) offer a limited number of free search queries. 															

Data Access Information

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1-01M												
Metric Name	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.												
Description	<p>This metric determines if the metadata includes the level of access to the data such as public, embargoed, restricted, or metadata-only access and its access conditions. Both access level and conditions are necessary information to potentially gain access to the data. It is recommended that data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are no access conditions for public data. Datasets should be released into the public domain (e.g., with an appropriate public-domain-equivalent license such as Creative Commons CC0 license) and openly accessible without restrictions when possible. • Embargoed access refers to data that will be made publicly accessible at a specific date. For example, a data author may release their data after having published their findings from the data. Therefore, access conditions such as the date the data will be released publicly is essential and should be specified in the metadata. • Restricted access refers to data that can be accessed under certain conditions (e.g. because of commercial, sensitive, or other confidentiality reasons or the data is only accessible via a subscription or a fee). Restricted data may be available to a particular group of users or after permission is granted. For restricted data, the metadata should include the conditions of access to the data such as point of contact or instructions to access the data. • Metadata-only access refers to data that is not made publicly available and for which only metadata is publicly available. 												
FAIR Principle	<p>A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol</p> <p>Note: This metric is about ensuring provision of metadata related to data access. This metadata is important to retrieve data using a standardized communication protocol, thus we mapped it to the principle A1.</p>												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	<p>R2. The repository maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance</p> <p>R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community</p>												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Data access information is machine readable</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	0.5	2	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms	1	3	Data access information is machine readable	1
level	test	score											
1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	0.5											
2	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms	1											
3	Data access information is machine readable	1											

Assessment	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata document.</p> <p>Check the presence/absence of data access level through metadata element(s). If it is embargoed data, check if the embargo end date is specified. If it is restricted data, check if the data access conditions are specified.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public domain licenses, https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain • EU Vocabulary on access rights, https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/at-dataset/-/resource/dataset/access-right • Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) Information Model 2.2, https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/ • Controlled Vocabulary for Access Rights, http://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/access_rights/ • Archival Access Rights Vocabulary (test vocabulary, not yet available through the production metadata registry), http://sandbox.metadatarregistry.org/concept/list/vocabulary_id/251.html • Eprints Access Rights Vocabulary Encoding Scheme, http://www.ukoln.ac.uk/repositories/digirep/index/Eprints_AccessRights_Vocabulary_Encoding_Scheme <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The metadata standard considered as part of the assessment may not include all of the elements for representing data access levels and related access information. The access information may be expressed in an unstructured manner, e.g., as a ‘comment’ in the metadata document. • The assessment of this metric only checks the metadata of access restrictions, but it does not validate if the access conditions specified are correct. • The assessment should be complemented with the evaluation of the data access mechanism based on the specified access levels, e.g., data is not accessible, accessible in a semi-automated (mediated access to data via data custodian), or automated fashion. • A data object may consist of several files with different access levels; some are with open access while others are with restricted access. So mixed access levels may apply to the object. 	

Standard Communication Protocol of Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1-02M
Metric Name	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
Description	Given an identifier of a dataset, the metadata of the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol. Consider, for example, the application layer protocols such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, TFTP, SFTP and AtomPub. Avoid disseminating metadata using a proprietary protocol (e.g., Apple Filing Protocol).
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol

CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.														
ASSESSMENT															
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) 														
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1			2			3	Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.	1		
level	test	score													
1															
2															
3	Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.	1													
Assessment	Use the data identifier to access its landing page (metadata document). Verify the application protocol used to serve the page based on the scheme part of the IRI. In case external metadata is linked to the landing page by typed links, use the data identifier specified in the typed link.														
COMMENTS															
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples of application layer protocols, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_layer IANA Protocol Registries, https://www.iana.org/protocols <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The metadata of a dataset may be shared in different ways (landing page, dedicated API, link relation type). The assessment assumes that the identifier resolves to a landing page (e.g., html) that contains the metadata of the dataset or includes typed links resolving to an external metadata resource. 															

Standard Communication Protocol of Data

FIELD	DESCRIPTION								
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1-03D								
Metric Name	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol								
Description	Given an identifier of a dataset, the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, TFTP, SFTP, FTAM and AtomPub. Avoid disseminating data using a proprietary protocol.								
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol								
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) 								
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score					
level	test	score							

	1		
	2		
	3	Metadata includes a resolvable link to data which is based on standardized web communication protocols.	1
Assessment	Check the application protocol of the data identifier based on the scheme part of the given IRI. In case external metadata is linked to the landing page by typed links, use the data identifier specified in the typed link.		
COMMENTS			
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples of application layer protocols, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_layer IANA Protocol Registries, https://www.iana.org/protocols <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Restricted or sensitive datasets may not be retrievable over the Web. Special authorization services may be required to retrieve these datasets from the data bank. 			

Metadata Preservation

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-A2-01M
Metric Name	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.
Description	This metric determines if the metadata will be preserved even when the data they represent are no longer available, replaced or lost. Similar to metric FsF-F4-01M , answering this metric will require an understanding of the capabilities offered, data preservation plan and policies implemented by the data repository and data services (e.g., Datacite PID service). Continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice which is usually documented in the repository's service policies or statements. A trustworthy data repository offering DOIs and implementing a PID Policy should guarantee that metadata will remain accessible even when data is no longer available for any reason (e.g., by providing a tombstone page)
FAIR Principle	A2. Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R10. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	--
Assessment	Programmatic assessment of the preservation of metadata of a data object can only be tested if the object is deleted or replaced. So this test is only applicable for deleted, replaced or obsolete objects. Importantly, continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice. Therefore, we regard that the assessment of metric applies to at the level of a repository, not at the level of

	<p>individual objects. For this reason, we excluded its assessment details from this specification.</p> <p>Depending on the supported persistent identifier type, some metadata may be by default preserved in a registry maintained by a PID provider (e.g. datacite). In addition to a repository’s preservation policy or statement, exchange protocol may indicate the status of records in an archive. For instance, OAI-PMH harvesting protocol which offers a field to declare one of three levels (no, persistent, and transient) of support for deleted records.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DMPonline, https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/public_plans • DMP Common Standards WG, https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg • ezDMP, https://ezdmp.org/index • Best Practices for offering tombstone pages, https://support.datacite.org/docs/tombstone-pages <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data preservation statements are usually found in a repository’s data policy or other governance documents. Machine-actionable representation of preservation policies in repository catalogues and registries such as re3data is important to enable an automated assessment of the statements. Further work in this areas is needed, for example to enable data producers to receive repository recommendations, based on preservation requirements expressed in machine-actionable DMPs, e.g., http://dx.doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v15i1.704 • Currently, PID providers (e.g., DataCite) do not offer any tombstone pages automatically for unavailable objects. Data providers may maintain the pages instead, for example https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.715333 	

Formal Representation of Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-I1-01M
Metric Name	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
Description	Knowledge representation is vital for machine-processing of the knowledge of a domain. Expressing the metadata of a data object using a formal knowledge representation will enable machines to process it in a meaningful way and enable more data exchange possibilities. Examples of knowledge representation languages are RDF, RDFS, and OWL. These languages may be serialized (written) in different formats. For instance, RDF/XML, RDFa, Notation3, Turtle, N-Triples and N-Quads, and JSON-LD are RDF serialization formats.
FAIR Principle	I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

	<p>Note: The I1 principle loosely defines the use of knowledge representation. Therefore, we define two metrics corresponding to the principle concerning metadata. The metric FsF-I1-01M focuses on making the metadata available for machine-mediated interpretation, whereas the metric FsF-I1-02M focuses on the use of semantic resources to enrich metadata.</p>												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	<p>R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data</p> <p>R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community</p>												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoint (e.g., SPARQL endpoint) 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1			2	Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code	1	3	Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint	2
level	test	score											
1													
2	Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code	1											
3	Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or sparql endpoint	2											
Assessment	<p>Machine-actionable representation (e.g., RDF) of the metadata may be retrieved as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If content negotiation is supported, use the identifier to perform a request, e.g., an RDF-based document. • Use the ‘typed links’ given in the HTML header section of the landing page to access the RDF-based metadata of the data, e.g., https://data.gov.lv/dati/lv/dataset/covid-19 • Query the SPARQL endpoint using the identifier (or optionally title) of the data, for example by using metadata elements from dcterms and dcat standards. Perform a full text-search within the SPARQL query if it is supported. 												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDF MIME types by serializer, http://librdf.org/raptor/api/raptor-formats-types-by-serializer.html • SPARQL Protocol for RDF, https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-protocol/ • Best Practice Recipes for Publishing RDF Vocabularies, https://www.w3.org/TR/swbp-vocab-pub/ • Community-defined models and formats via FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/?q=&selected_facets=type_exact:model/format <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on a data identifier, it is not possible to programmatically discover the SPARQL endpoint provided by a data repository, unless the endpoint information is specified in the repository metadata, e.g., https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100012203 • The RDF-based metadata may not be supported by the data repository which curates the data, but it may be available through external linked data repositories, e.g., bio2rdf. 													

- RDF data may be serialized in a number of different ways. Therefore, the variety of serialization formats (and their respective MIME types) should be considered when performing the SPARQL query.

Metadata with Semantic Resources

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-I1-02M												
Metric Name	Metadata uses semantic resources.												
Description	<p>A metadata document or selected parts of the document may incorporate additional terms from semantic resources (also referred as semantic artefacts) that unambiguously describe the contents so they can be processed automatically by machines. This metadata enrichment may facilitate enhanced data search and interoperability of data from different sources.</p> <p>Ontology, thesaurus, and taxonomy are kinds of semantic resources, and they come with varying degrees of expressiveness and computational complexity. Knowledge organization schemes such as thesaurus and taxonomy are semantically less formal than ontologies.</p>												
FAIR Principle	I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	<p>R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data</p> <p>R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community</p>												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoint (SPARQL endpoint) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata • Registry of semantic resources 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata		2			3	Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata	1
level	test	score											
1	Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata												
2													
3	Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata	1											
Assessment	<p>This assessment is the continuation of the assessment FsF-I1-01M, but focuses on the metadata contents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract namespaces declared from the machine-actionable metadata document. Filter out common namespaces (e.g., rdf, rdfs, xsd, owl). • Compare the remaining namespaces with entries from existing (known) ontology registries (see examples listed in Related Resources). 												
COMMENTS													

Related Resources

- Publishing and consuming Linked Data embedded in HTML, <https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/interest/ldh/>
- Examples of repositories or look-up services for semantic resources (the list is not exhaustive):
 - Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV), <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov>
 - OBO Foundry, <http://www.obofoundry.org/>
 - BioPortal, <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>
 - Basel Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications (BARTOC), <https://bartoc.org/>
 - NERC Vocabulary Server, <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>
 - Research Vocabulary Australia, <https://vocabs.andis.org.au/>
 - MMI Ontology Registry and Repository (ORR), <https://mmisw.org/>
 - Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF), <https://www.industrialontologies.org/>
 - CESSDA Vocabulary Service, <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/>
 - FAIRsharing terminology artifact, https://fairsharing.org/standards/?q=&selected_facets=type_exact:terminology%20artifact

Known Limitations/Constraints

- The assessment checks the inclusion of semantic markup in the metadata page, not their contents and quality, e.g., if the terms used are in appropriate context and accessible over the web.
- There is no up-to-date, maintained, cross domain ontology catalogue, registry or ontology library available.
- It is hard to verify if the metadata uses FAIR vocabularies as the criteria defining a FAIR vocabulary have not fully developed and recommended yet.

Links to Related Entities

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-I3-01M
Metric Name	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.
Description	Linking data to its related entities will increase its potential for reuse. The linking information should be captured as part of the metadata. A dataset may be linked to its prior version, related datasets or resources (e.g. publication, physical sample, funder, repository, platform, site, or observing network registries). Links between data and its related entities should be expressed through relation types (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema specifies relation types between research objects through the fields 'RelatedIdentifier' and 'RelationType'), and preferably use persistent Identifiers for related entities (e.g., ORCID for contributors, DOI for publications, and ROR for institutions).
FAIR Principle	I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R11. The repository has appropriate expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations

ASSESSMENT		
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 	
Compliance Levels	level	test
	1	
	2	Related resources are explicitly mentioned in metadata
	3	Related resources are indicated by machine readable links or identifiers
Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. • Check the metadata elements which indicate the relationship between data and related entities. • Test if the URLs of the related entities are active (not broken links). 	
COMMENTS		
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2019). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3, https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69 • Link Relation Types, https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different metadata schemas may use different properties to specify the relation between data and its related entities. • The assessment regards any relation between a data and its related entities as success. It does not consider the quantity or types of relations. • Links to related resources are not necessarily expressed as actionable links but may also be strings such as citations. 		

Metadata of Data Content

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1-01MD
Metric Name	Metadata specifies the content of the data.
Description	This metric evaluates if the content of the dataset is specified in the metadata, and it should be an accurate reflection of the actual data deposited. Examples of the properties specifying data content are resource type (e.g., data or a collection of data), variable(s) measured or observed, method, data format and size. Ideally, ontological vocabularies should be used to describe data content (e.g., variable) to support interdisciplinary reuse.
FAIR Principle	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes Note: Data quality aspect is not explicitly addressed by FAIR principles. However, an accurate description of the data content is important for assessing the quality of

	the data. We regard the properties of data content as part of rich metadata, therefore we map this metric to its closest principle R1.												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R11. The repository has appropriate expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Identifier • Machine-accessible and readable metadata • Data file(s) 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata (resource type, links)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Verifiable data descriptors (file info (size, type), measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata</td> <td>+1 (var) +1 (file)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Data content matches measured variables or file type and size specified in metadata</td> <td>+1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata (resource type, links)	1	2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info (size, type), measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	+1 (var) +1 (file)	3	Data content matches measured variables or file type and size specified in metadata	+1
level	test	score											
1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata (resource type, links)	1											
2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info (size, type), measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	+1 (var) +1 (file)											
3	Data content matches measured variables or file type and size specified in metadata	+1											
Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Verify the presence/absence of elements representing data content descriptions in the metadata document. • Use the data access URL specified in the metadata to retrieve the actual data. Check if ontology terms are used to describe data content. • Compare the content descriptions found with actual data properties (see comment* below). 												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frictionless Data, https://frictionlessdata.io/ • CSV on the Web: A Primer, https://www.w3.org/TR/tabular-data-primer/ • Apache Tika (an example of content analysis toolkit), https://tika.apache.org/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • *The proposed assessment has some general limitations and some cases where future expansion is dependent on contexts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Descriptors (mandatory and optional properties of a schema) may influence metadata completeness. ○ Validation of descriptor content is beyond the scope of this test as it would depend on human judgement. ○ A detailed assessment of data files properties would depend on some agreed mechanism for defining and agreeing domain requirements. • General-purpose metadata standards such as Datacite Metadata Schema and Schema.org provide elements to represent content descriptions. Thus, it is possible to check programmatically if the descriptions required are present in the metadata. However, the conformance/matching test may become a challenge due to a variety of data types and data size. Standardized tabular data and self-describing data formats (e.g., HDF, NetCDF, Parquet) are promising, but not the solution to every 													

research domain. Another challenge is that unstructured content descriptions might be included in a data file; fuzzy text-matching algorithms can be useful here.

Data Usage License

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.1-01M												
Metric Name	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.												
Description	<p>This metric evaluates if data is associated with a license because otherwise users cannot reuse it in a clear legal context. We encourage the application of licenses for all kinds of data whether public, restricted or for specific users. Without an explicit license, users do not have a clear idea of what can be done with your data. Licenses can be of standard type (Creative Commons, Open Data Commons Open Database License) or bespoke licenses, and rights statements which indicate the conditions under which data can be reused.</p> <p>It is highly recommended to use a standard, machine-readable license such that it can be interpreted by machines and humans. In order to inform users about what rights they have to use a dataset, the license information should be specified as part of the dataset's metadata.</p>												
FAIR Principle	R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R2. The repository maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Recognized licence is valid, actionable and registered at SPDX</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element	1	2			3	Recognized licence is valid, actionable and registered at SPDX	2
level	test	score											
1	Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element	1											
2													
3	Recognized licence is valid, actionable and registered at SPDX	2											
Assessment	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata document.</p> <p>Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to license information of the data.</p> <p>The license information (e.g., name or URI) may be used to request additional information (e.g., OSI approved) from an external license registry (e.g., SPDX).</p>												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPDX license registry, https://spdx.org/licenses/ • Rights statements of cultural heritage objects, https://rightsstatements.org/page/1.0/?language=en 													

- ARDC Data Rights Management Guide, <https://ardc.edu.au/guides/research-data-rights-management>
- The Landscape of Rights and Licensing Initiatives for Data Sharing, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-029>
- Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>
- Creative Commons, <https://creativecommons.org/>
- Creative Commons Rights Expression Language, <https://creativecommons.org/ns>

Known Limitations/Constraints

- The assessment checks if the license information is provided as part of the metadata. It does not validate if the specified license is the most appropriate license for the data. There may be quite specific circumstances related to the data that cannot be explicitly expressed in the metadata as to why a license was chosen.
- As part of the future improvement, the assessment of the metric may take into account several aspects of a data license such as (i) standard or bespoke license and (ii) machine-readability of license.

Data Provenance

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.2-01M
Metric Name	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
Description	<p>Data provenance (also known as lineage) represents a dataset’s history, including the people, entities, and processes involved in its creation, management and longer-term curation. It is essential that data producers provide provenance information about the data to enable informed use and reuse. The levels of provenance information needed can vary depending on the data type (e.g., measurement, observation, derived data, or data product) and research domains. For that reason, it is difficult to define a set of finite provenance properties that will be adequate for all domains. Based on existing work, we suggest that the following provenance properties of data generation or collection are included in the metadata record as a minimum.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sources of data, e.g., datasets the data is derived from and instruments ● Data creation or collection date ● Contributors involved in data creation and their roles ● Data publication, modification and versioning information <p>There are various ways through which provenance information may be included in a metadata record. Some of the provenance properties (e.g., instrument, contributor) may be best represented using PIDs (such as DOIs for data, ORCIDs for researchers). This way, humans and systems can retrieve more information about each of the properties by resolving the PIDs. Alternatively, the provenance</p>

	information can be given in a linked provenance record expressed explicitly in, e.g., PROV-O or PAV or Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VoID).												
FAIR Principle	R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R7. The repository guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) Machine-accessible and readable metadata 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1			2	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV	1	3	Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)	2
level	test	score											
1													
2	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV	1											
3	Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)	2											
Assessment	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to the minimum data provenance properties.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presence of basic ‘proxy’ metadata elements related to data creation (creator, contributors, date, and version, modification date, etc.) Presence of process indicator, e.g. dc:source or relation type (isVersionOf, isBasedOn, isFormatOf) addressed in FsF-I3-01M. Presence of PROV-O or PAV information in RDFa microformats (landing page) or in RDF metadata. 												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PROV Model Primer, https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-primer/ Dublin Core to PROV Mapping, https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dc/ Checklist for Evaluation of Dataset Fitness for Use produced by the WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG, https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/DataFitnessForUse_ChecklistForm_v2_20181218_RDADistribution.pdf W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices (8.4 Data Provenance), https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#metadata PROV-O as RDFa, https://www.w3.org/2011/prov/wiki/PROV-O_as_RDF OPMV, the Open Provenance Model Vocabulary, http://purl.org/net/opmv/ns Business Process Model and Notation, https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/ PAV- Provenance, Authoring and Versioning ontology: https://pav-ontology.github.io/pav/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The proposed minimum provenance properties are not final; new properties may be incorporated into the assessment if the requirement emerges. Properties such as processes/methods (incl. model, instrument, etc.) used in the data creation depend on domain standards. 													

- We regard references to related works (scholarly articles, data papers, preceding or associated data) as useful provenance information. This property of provenance is considered as part of [FsF-I3-01M](#), therefore we excluded it from the assessment.
- Metadata may include a specific element (e.g., dcmi:provenance) and/or ‘proxy’ elements (e.g., datacite:Contributor, schema.org:measurementTechnique) to convey data provenance.
- Data may be published at different analysis stages (raw, processed, derivative, product). The completeness of the provenance information may depend on the stage at which the data is published.

Community Metadata Standard

FIELD	DESCRIPTION												
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-01M												
Metric Name	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.												
Description	In addition to core metadata required to support data discovery (covered under metric FsF-F2-01M), metadata to support data reusability should be made available following community-endorsed metadata standards. Some communities have well-established metadata standards (e.g., geospatial: ISO19115; biodiversity: DarwinCore, ABCD, EML; social science: DDI; astronomy: International Virtual Observatory Alliance Technical Specifications) while others have limited standards or standards that are under development (e.g., engineering and linguistics). The use of community-endorsed metadata standards is usually encouraged and supported by domain and discipline-specific repositories.												
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards												
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoints including SPARQL endpoint 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1			2	Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository	1	3	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs	1
level	test	score											
1													
2	Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository	1											
3	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs	1											
Assessment	<p>Gather all metadata standards used by a data repository; this list can be requested, e.g., from the metadata endpoint (e.g., OAI-PMH). Filter out domain-agnostic standards (e.g., Datacite Metadata Schema, Dublin Core, Schema.org) from the list. Cross check the remaining standards with an external metadata registry, e.g., RDA Metadata Standards Catalog.</p> <p>Request metadata of the data identifier specified based on one of the remaining standards as a test case (see comment* below).</p>												
COMMENTS													

Related Resources

Examples of the metadata standards with subject areas:

- DCC List of Metadata Standards, <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/list>
- RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>
- FAIRsharing, <https://fairsharing.org/standards/>
- OAI-PMH Data Provider Validation and Registration, <https://www.openarchives.org/Register/ValidateSite>
- OAI-PMH Tools, <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/tools/>
- Metadata standards supported by a repository may be available through re3data, <https://www.re3data.org/>

Known Limitations/Constraints

- *The data identifier provided (e.g., PID) may not be the same as the identifier used in the metadata record harvested. For example, in OAI-PMH, the nature of a record identifier is outside the scope of the harvesting protocol; for more information, see <http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html#UniqueIdentifier>
- The assessment focuses on a specific metadata harvesting protocol. It might not be supported by all data repositories.
- Future evaluation of the metric should also consider the extent to which the metadata of a dataset reflects the community-endorsed metadata standard.
- Some of these discipline-specific standards might not be properly formalized so an automatic validation of the metadata based on the standards can be problematic. External tools might be necessary to check compliance with metadata standards.

Data File Format

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-02D
Metric Name	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.
Description	File formats refer to methods for encoding digital information. For example, CSV for tabular data, NetCDF for multidimensional data and GeoTIFF for raster imagery. Data should be made available in a file format that is backed by the research community to enable data sharing and reuse. Consider for example, file formats that are widely used and supported by the most commonly used software and tools. These formats also should be suitable for long-term storage and archiving, which are usually recommended by a data repository. The formats not only give a higher certainty that your data can be read in the future, but they will also help to increase the reusability and interoperability. Using community-endorsed formats enables data to be loaded directly into the software and tools used for data analysis. It makes it possible to easily integrate your data with other data using the same preferred format. The use of community-endorsed formats will also help to transform the format to a newer one, in case an older format gets outdated.
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community												
ASSESSMENT													
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) Machine-accessible and readable metadata 												
Compliance Levels	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>level</th> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>The format of the data file is an open format</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>The format of the data file is a long term format</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>The format of the data file is a scientific format</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	level	test	score	1	The format of the data file is an open format	1	2	The format of the data file is a long term format	1	3	The format of the data file is a scientific format	1
level	test	score											
1	The format of the data file is an open format	1											
2	The format of the data file is a long term format	1											
3	The format of the data file is a scientific format	1											
Assessment	Extract file format information (mime-type) from the metadata based on elements, e.g., datacite:Format, schema.org: fileFormat, dc:format. Check if the format is an open and long-term file format (see comment* below).												
COMMENTS													
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A list of commonly used as well as domain specific scientific file formats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://justsolve.archiveteam.org/index.php/Scientific_Data_formats https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_file_formats#Scientific_data_(data_exchange) Examples of recommended file formats based on data types, https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/format/recommended-formats.aspx PRONOM file format registry, https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Format/proFormatSearch.aspx?status=new A recommended format statement by the US Library of Congress, https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs Long-term file formats: ISO/TR 22299. Document management - Digital file format recommendations for long-term storage, https://www.iso.org/standard/73117.html File type support lists provided by open source and commercial statistics (e.g. https://de.mathworks.com/help/matlab/import_export/supported-file-formats.html) or spreadsheet processing software vendors (e.g. https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/file-formats-that-are-supported-in-excel-0943ff2c-6014-4e8d-aaea-b83d51d46247?ui=en-us&rs=en-us&ad=us). <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *At present, there is a lack of reference resources (registries) against which a file format test can be checked programmatically. Common file formats endorsed by communities are not available through a registry but on static web pages (see resources above). This is an issue for the scientific community as a whole. Further work is needed to develop a standard approach to defining which formats are open and suitable for long-term preservation and use and managing those community-specific lists over time. 													

- Not all data can be made available in an open, non-proprietary, widely supported format, such as most 3D data, CAD data, dynamic spreadsheets or databases with specific significant characteristics which cannot be exported.
- Standard formats in earth system modeling (atmosphere, ocean) are netCDF and GRIB. GRIB is used for internal storage rather than for publication.
- Commonly used community file formats are not necessarily very domain specific. Some very generic file formats for e.g. spreadsheets are widely used by the scientific community.
- Data files may be made available using an archive file format (e.g., *.zip). In addition to the archive format, the actual file formats should be specified in the metadata such that machines can extract/unzip the downloaded file and read the actual files programmatically.
- Many scientific formats do not have an associated mime-type (e.g. BUFR), thus are hard to detect.

Appendix B - Additional use cases

As noted in section 1, FAIRsFAIR is focusing on addressing two distinct use cases. These are:

- raising awareness of researchers about how to make their data FAIR before they deposit with an appropriate data archive (Scenarios 1&2 in Figure 1).
- assessing the FAIRness of research data held in trustworthy data archives (Scenarios 6&7 in Figure 1).

However, in our initial desk research, we explored a number of additional assessment use cases scenarios as is shown in Figure 1 (see Introduction).

In the table below, we present these additional scenarios for assessment and provide some initial ideas about badging that may be associated with each.

Table 3: Use cases for the FAIR assessment of data across the research data lifecycle and their potential for using badges to indicate the results

Short Description of Use Case	Related Lifecycle stage(s)	Potential for badging (if applicable)
Researchers want to check their data management plans for producing FAIR data at the outset of their project and to periodically assess FAIRness over the life of their project. (Scenario 3)	Planning Research; Collecting Data; Processing and Analyzing Data	<p>Data Management Plans (DMPs) could be badged as being <i>FAIR-enabling</i> during initial and periodic assessment.</p> <p>This would be largely a supported self-assessment and the resulting badge would be assigned by the Research Performing Organisation (RPO).</p> <p>This badge could serve as a form of evidence for funding bodies that DMPs have been reviewed and deemed to be practically implementable by local support staff.</p> <p>There is potential to explore the feasibility of integrating badging of this nature into DMP tools to support the validation of automated approval and monitoring workflows.</p>
<p>Researchers want to check that their data is as FAIR as possible before depositing the data in a repository for wider sharing (e.g., using FAIR-Aware as detailed in section 5.1). (Scenario 1)</p> <p>Researchers want to ensure that their data is as FAIR as possible during the</p>	Processing and Analyzing Data; Publishing and Sharing Data	<p>This assessment would be carried out at the researcher and Research Performing Organisation (RPO) level as part of the project completion stage (e.g., end-stage DMP). Data meeting the threshold could be badged as being <i>FAIR and ready for deposit</i>. The threshold for FAIRness should reflect community norms and practices such as those outlined in</p>

<p>deposit process with a data repository. (Scenario 4)</p>		<p>FAIR Implementation Profiles⁸² or similarly community-agreed level.</p> <p>This would be largely a supported self-assessment and the resulting badge would be assigned by the RPO.</p> <p>The badge could be used to provide evidence to funding bodies that selected data produced in the life of a project are FAIR and could also help to make the deposit process more streamlined and efficient at the repository end.</p>
<p>Data repositories want to make it easier for depositors to provide FAIR data at the point of submission. (Scenario 2)</p> <p>Data repositories want to assess data deposits for FAIRness during ingest. (Scenario 5)</p>	<p>Publishing and Sharing Data</p>	<p>Repositories may carry out their own assessment on whether data are <i>FAIR and ready for deposit</i> prior to accepting the data.</p> <p>This assessment may be different to the assessment carried out at the RPO level and may reflect specific standards relating to metadata and PIDs that are supported by the repository.</p> <p>The assessment will validate the results of the self-assessment outlined above. In some cases, a successful self-assessment may fail and remedial action on the part of the depositor may be necessary prior to acceptance.</p> <p>These assessments can help repositories to identify common challenges and problematic areas where guidance may be needed in relation to supported and/or preferred metadata standards and PIDs. Such guidance could be pushed upstream to RPOs to help ensure that researchers aiming to deposit in a particular repository can adequately address specific requirements in their DMPs and facilitate smoother transfer to repositories.</p>
<p>Funding bodies may want to monitor compliance with their requirements relating to FAIR (meta)data sharing. (Scenario 8)</p>	<p>Preserving Data; Re-using Data</p>	<p>Funding bodies may wish to monitor the badging of DMPs when evaluating them as part of the wider project application.</p> <p>An assessment of datasets that are submitted in trustworthy repositories can help a funder to get a picture of overall compliance with their FAIR data sharing policies.</p>
<p>Data repositories want to periodically re-assess the FAIRness of the datasets they hold (e.g., using F-UJI as detailed in section 5.2). (Scenario 6)</p>	<p>Publishing and Sharing Data; Preserving Data, Re-using Data</p>	<p>Repositories may want to offer badges for deposited datasets to indicate how FAIR their collections and individual datasets are</p>

⁸² <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

		<p>to end users and thus encourage the re-use of datasets.</p> <p>A regular assessment of datasets can also help repositories understand how they support FAIRness over time and identify areas for improvement in their technical setup and guidance for deposits. This also increases transparency for the users of the repository in accordance with the TRUST⁸³ principles.</p>
<p>Certification bodies may want to understand how repositories support their users in making their datasets FAIR. (Senario 7)</p>	<p>Publishing and Sharing Data</p>	<p>Certification bodies may want to use badges provided by repositories to support their decision on certifying a repository on aspects such as FAIR-enabling datasets and FAIRness of digital objects in their collection.</p>

The additional scenarios show that while different stakeholders will have different motivations for carrying out assessments, the results of the assessments can be beneficial for improving the FAIRness of data and improving the quality and efficiency of related services. Our initial ideas around badging for each of these additional use cases indicates that there are areas where the results of one assessment could be used to make another assessment activity more efficient or to ensure that the results are more reliable. There could be value in carrying out further work on the feasibility of developing shared workflows and pipelines where the results of various assessments can be shared and used to support decision-making, improve workflows, and lead to a stronger evidence base both for the FAIRness of research outputs and the quality of data services.

⁸³ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>